

Aligning herders with society for wildfire prevention: economic incentives and collective action

Abstract

The present study explores the economic nature and property rights related to the provision of forest fire prevention. Fire protection is consumed collectively and can be co-produced by beneficiaries. Hence, we test features that may facilitate agents' coordination in the emergence of decentralized solutions, and the role economic incentives and government intervention may have for a successful low risk maintenance. A review of scholar literature on common-pool resources and public goods allow for distinguish forest-related problems in the Mediterranean and establish the framework for analysing facilitating factors for collective action. Several case studies have been assessed in this frame, namely: public contracts with shepherds, public grants for herders and voluntary agreements private forest owners-herders, always with the purpose of lowering biomass in fuel breaks for fire prevention. Accumulation of shrub biomass in forests is a relatively recent phenomenon, what may preclude for successful, spontaneous self-management solutions. Government involvement is present in all cases in different degrees and is justified by the conservation of forest externalities to society at large. Results show that external (usually government) support is required for catalyzing agreements and covering start-up expenses. There is a large expectation in this pastoral approach, seen as potentially more financially sustainable than traditional mechanical interventions, given the reduced costs for the administration while it also provides a marketable product. Secondary benefits accrue: an innovation in the social role of herders, incentives for indigenous cattle races conservation and better coordination between departments. Compensation payments are seen as a deserved reward for the effort incurred by herders due to grazing in less attractive areas for their business. Private owners' agreements with herders are more likely to take place in areas with previous experiences of cooperation, high risk perception and with potential grant for herders. Normative measures that oblige the direct beneficiaries to take care of their own fire prevention may also induce to similar programmes. In general, society is still unaware about these initiatives.

Keywords:

Property rights, Payment for Environmental Services, controlled grazing, preventive silviculture, Mediterranean forests

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BACKGROUND

1. Environmental problems linked to pastures in the Mediterranean

The long-lasting human interaction with Mediterranean forest ecosystems has caused, on one side, the development of social arrangements on how to manage forest areas, and on the other side certain ecosystem dynamics that are human-dependent (becoming human actions part of ecosystem processes). However, the deep global (social and climatic) changes in the last decades have configured a new scenario, with different resulting problems in the Northern and the Southern rim of the Mediterranean basin. Whereas in the South and East the current trend is the overexploitation of the resource, in the North there is an abandonment of the activity. Bugalho et al (2011) identify the consequences of both extreme situations (horizontal axis in figure 1) and estimate the sustainable use somewhere in a middle position. The causes underlying these problems have been ascribed to economic factors, such as the “active rural population” in the Southern rim (Bugalho et al, 2011) or to low income per capita and limited diversification of activities in rural areas (Palahi et al, 2008), and the lack of manpower and profitability in the Northern rim (Palahi et al, 2008; Bugalho et al, 2011). Bugalho et al (2011) suggest that incentives in line with Payments for Environmental Services (PES) can facilitate the transition to the sustainable use level. For the overexploitation of forest they suggest the REDD (Reduced Emissions from Deforestation and Degradation) program, whereas for the abandonment case they suggest product certification schemes, what is expected to encourage management by better market prices. The rationale behind the first instruments is a compensation to traditional forest users for restricting their uses, this, an *activity-capping* program; the second is, on the contrary, an *activity-enhancing* instrument, seeking to reward forest managers for an effective execution of certain sustainable measures. It becomes clear that the type of action to promote differs according to the nature of the problem.

Figure - Ecosystem services provided by cork oak savannas depend on the intensity of human use. Source: Bugalho et al, 2011.

A relevant land use related to the abovementioned problems is the use of forests for grazing. Pastures constitute a natural resource, composed of the edible biomass -shrubs and herbs- that cattle eat when bred in an extensive manner. In the Southern and Eastern Mediterranean overgrazing is one of the main challenges jeopardizing forest regeneration (Berrahmouni et al, 2007). On the other hand, extensive grazing may reduce wildfire risk and improve biodiversity in the Northern countries (Baiges et al, 2007).

2. Economic nature of previous problems

Samuelson (1954) differentiated between “ordinary private consumption goods”, understood as those able to be “parcelled out among different individuals”; and “collective consumption goods, which all enjoy in common the sense

that each individual's consumption of such a good leads to no subtraction from any other individual's consumption of that good". Buchanan (1965) noted that there are other options between the purely private/purely public of goods; he proposed an intermediate option where beneficiaries can be excluded but they consume collectively: "club goods". Later, Ostrom and Ostrom (1977) proposed a fourth type of good, the "common-pool goods" for those non-excludable but subtractable goods. They also suggested that concepts of excludability or rivalry are better characterized by varying from low to high, this is, with a range of intermediate degrees, rather than by their presence or absence. This conceptualisation allows for understanding a congestion threshold in some ("impure") public goods, referred to the situation where the use of the public good by an additional agent creates costs on the other users. Based on these definitions, economic goods are generally defined by their rivalry and accessibility characteristics, classifying them in four typologies: public, common-pool, club or private good, as presented in . Rivalry refers to the consumptive use: a good is *rival* if its enjoyment by one agent impedes the enjoyment by another, because it is no longer available. Excludability refers to the ability to have access to enjoy the good.

Table - Good characterisation according to rivalry and excludability criteria

	Rival	No rival
Excludable	Private good	Club good
Non-excludable	Common-pool good	Public good

Maintenance of natural resources, as well as other economic goods, may require **investments**. Investment here is considered as direct inputs (e.g. labor, money) for natural resources management, but also as those opportunity costs in terms of sacrifices that agents do for respecting regeneration rates as well as those efforts in view of improving the resource. Investments are largely dependent on the abovementioned characteristics of the good: non-excludable goods are subject to *free-riding*, given that by definition no one can preclude an agent from benefiting from the good even if s/he is not contributing by investing on it. In this way, agents incurring in investments in a collectively consumed good (public or common-pool) are creating externalities to others.

2.1. Overgrazing in Southern and Eastern Mediterranean: a common-pool resource issue

Ownership of forests and pastures

Southern and Eastern Mediterranean countries have a strong influence of Ottoman tradition concerning land tenure, by which state land covers most uncultivated, so called "dead" land or *mawat*, which includes grazing lands operated under common property regimes, this is, managed and customarily owned by a certain community according to sets of rules and rights, including individual usufruct but not individual disposal (Forni, 2005). Uncultivated areas are usually those with low marginal productivity for agriculture and the reason behind leaving those areas for everyman's use was to facilitate some resources to poorest agents in rural societies.

Seen the overgrazing problems, it is rather straightforward to make the relationship with the so-called "tragedy of the commons", which was precisely exemplified by the case of pastures in open access fields (Hardin, 1968). Hardin described how individuals' rationality of pursuing maximum benefit by taking into account only one's costs (and not the costs caused to others) leads to an overuse of a commonly owned resource. He attributed the traditional maintenance of the recourse to the numerical control of human beings due to violent conflicts, but once those conflicts cease and populations increase, "*the inherent logic of the commons remorselessly generates tragedy*". Hardin (1968) suggested, then, that private ownership or state property allocating the rights to enter into the commons would entail a more durable use of the resource.

Critics to Commons tragedy

Common-Pool Resources (CPR) are defined as natural or human-made resources that share two attributes: (i) substantial difficulty (but not impossibility) of devising ways to exclude individuals from benefiting from these resources; and (ii) the subtractability of benefits consumed by one individual from those available to others (Ostrom,

2009). Usually, commons scholars differentiate between the intrinsic characteristics of the good or service under study, determined by its ecological and physical features, and the formal and informal institutional arrangements that facilitate the access' control or its consumptive use. Both, intrinsic characteristics and institutional arrangement do shape the final economic character as explained in Table .

The main critic to Hardin's article has been the confusion between an "open access" good and the concept of "common ownership". Free access to a resource and the absence of agreements governing extraction (Fisher, 1981, cited in Aguilera-Klink, 1994) leads the actual problem of the rule of capture. On the other side, if property exists, there is no unrestricted access to resources anywhere (Aguilera-Klink, 1994). Therefore a common property good is not an "everybody's property", this is, it is not a "*res nullius*" subject to anyone's harvest (Boriaud and Schmithüßen, 2005), but instead it has several individual owners, and hence they will face incentives for conservation. Commons scholars have attempted to show that there is a broader range of plausible institutional mechanisms than the typical individual/private or state ownership (Agrawal, 2003). Empirical studies show that no single type of property regime works always efficiently, fairly and sustainable in relation to all CPR (Ostrom et al, 1999).

Property rights are historically developed, socially accepted as part of the "social contract", and dynamic in the medium/long term. Who determines them is a key question that goes from the formal legislator to the informal local agreements. Formal rights are established by legislators, but are not effective in practice without a proper enforcement: the motivations that influence the compliance decision include instrumental benefits and costs, social and personal norms, and legitimacy (Ramcilovic-Suominen, 2012). On the other hand, customary rights are difficult to be changed by legislators, given that such a change may develop into social opposition responses affecting their political economy (e.g. in a democratic society that may cause a reduction in votes). However, customary rights may be originated in traditional societies whose socio-economic conditions may have been altered in the last times modifying ecosystem service quantity or quality. Agrawal (2003) points out the relevance of demographic changes, technology availability and market structure as potential factor that can modify traditional patterns of use towards sustainable outcomes. Evolved norms, hence, are not always sufficient to prevent overexploitation (Ostrom et al. 1999). In these cases, certain policy actions may be required to modify natural resource use patterns of local communities and direct users of the resources.

Economic nature of pastures

Herders' final products are clearly a private good and have their markets developed. The process of breeding the animals is what affects forest sustainability: an overuse of pastures may lead to a lack of natural regeneration. The pasture resource is usually in the Mediterranean in open fields; and it is easy to understand that the grass pastured by the animals of one herder cannot be eaten by other, hence being rival. From these natural/physical characteristics, one could classify the good as a **common-pool resource**. Nevertheless is the excludability possible by physical or social means, this is, fencing (e.g. stone walls, wooden gates) or limiting access through establishing signs of parcel delimitation (e.g. landmarks or plaques) and enforcing them. Their respect can vary according to the monetary or social sanctioning: breaching the agreements may exclude an individual from the local group; on the contrary, the probability of monetary sanctions lower than the potential market benefits may discourage compliance. On the other side, pastures can be of **common property**, meaning that the management belong to the community as a group, not to individuals. When there is no coordination, no cooperation among herders, the rule of capture may prevail most likely leading to the so-called tragedy, as Hardin was predicting. It can also occur that community agents may have evolved certain norms on the use of those lands, therefore limiting access, creating a sort of impure private good.

Policies to overcome the CPR problem

Some Eastern and Southern Mediterranean countries have acknowledged the problems related to overgrazing. They have generally introduced public reforestation programs and/or a set of command and control policies. Forni (2005)

reports that “rules and regulations proposed by governments are often intended to control rather than to support the producers. This partly explains the reluctance of many pastoralists in the region to participate in public programmes, because they suspect hidden motives”.

As an alternative to the imposition, economic incentives emerge as a new instrument to attempt the desired control of grazing. In this line, Morocco is implementing since 2002 the principle of compensation to traditional users (M’Hirit and Benchenkroun, 2006). It consists of a governmental programme of fencing forest areas jointly with a mechanism of payments to shepherds associations to compensate their losses due to the set aside forest areas (Arrêté 1855-01, 2002¹). The programme is funded by the National Forest Fund, whose budget stems from harvesting fees. The norm establishes an annual amount of 350DHM/ha, but this amount does not go directly to the users but instead is reverted in form of projects for the local community. By 2011, 134 associations participated grouping 15.000 members covering 278.000ha (Aouni, 2012). The payment could be interpreted then as an incentive to motivate pasture users in coordinating their behaviours, what would be rewarded collectively by covering common-shared necessities.

2.2. Wildfires in Northern Mediterranean countries: a public bad problem

The decrease of pasturing in the Northern rim jointly with the abandonment of silvicultural activities (e.g. thinnings, pruning, fuel wood harvesting) have resulted in an accumulation of biomass in forests. Climatic changing conditions moving towards a drier and warmer seasons make easier the ignition and spread of wildfires.

Large wildfires are a relatively new phenomenon in the recent history of the Mediterranean basin (Pausas et al, 2008). Most of the resources devoted by government have been addressed towards the extinction of fires. This has created the so-called “fire paradox” by which the systematic avoidance of any small fire allows an accumulation of fuel such that it increases the probability of big, high intensity wildfires (Fernandes, 2008). Therefore, the paradigm in the last decade is moving towards fire prevention measures that produce more resilient landscapes, assuming that fire may take place at some point: the denominated “living with wildfires” (Biro, 2009). In this line, main fire policies’ objectives and measures are exposed in Table :

Table - Objectives of fire prevention policies and measures. Source: own elaboration based on Vélez (2000).

Objective	Examples of measures
Reduction of fire ignition probability (<i>fire hazard</i>)	dissuasive surveillance, awareness campaigns, harder sanctions and causes’ investigation, forest access prohibition
Reduction of fire spread (<i>fire intensity, extent</i>)	disconnecting surface fuel with tree crown, compartmentalize forest with fuelbreaks
Facilitation of extinction (<i>fire intensity, extent</i>)	quick alert, firemen secure access through firebreaks and roads, water points, aerial and terrestrial teams
Reduction of fire impact (<i>vulnerability, severity</i>)	Reforestations with native species, security perimeters around buildings, improving forest resilience

Economic nature of wildfire prevention

For the purpose of this study, we will base on Kron’s (2002) definition of “risk”², assimilated to the expected losses as the product of a hazard and its consequences. Three variables determine the risk: “hazard”, understood as the event itself and its likelihood of occurrence; “vulnerability”, as the lack of resistance to damaging/ destructive forces; and “exposure”, as values and/or humans that are present at the location involved (e.g. the trees, the environmental

¹ Arrêté du ministre délégué auprès du ministre de l’agriculture, du développement rural et des eaux et forêts, chargé des eaux et forêts no 1855-01 du 6 moharrem 1423 (21 mars UHIZ) fixant les limites, conditions et modalités de demande et d’octroi de la compensation pour mises en défens du domaine forestier à exploiter ou à régénérer.

² We take this terminology as a broader than the usual within the fire community, where “fire risk” refers only to the probability that a fire might start (Hardy, 2005; Keeley et al, 2009).

services they provide or buildings). Vulnerability depends on the extinction efforts devoted but also on the intrinsic characteristics of the good to resist and recover from fire. "Fire intensity" refers to the behaviour of the fire, in terms of spread velocity, flame length, etc. Generally tree crown fires are intense fires, and with harsh weather conditions they can easier develop into the so-called "big fires" (those over 500ha burnt, according to Spanish statistics system). "Fire severity" will refer specifically to the actual effects or impacts a fire has on wildland systems (Hardy, 2005). Severity entails the impacts of exposed human values as a result from vulnerability, fire intensity and extinction efforts. Severity is linked to resilience of the ecosystem, given that Mediterranean forests have capacity of natural recovery: low intensity fires will presumably be followed by a natural regeneration capable to restore previous ecosystem conditions in the medium-term, while high intensity fires may put in question such natural processes, and hence require human intervention to ensure the forest restoration. It should be noted that the probability of fire occurrence is hard to be assessed; historical fire maps and analysis of causes, information on weather or vegetation conditions may provide a insights on a probabilistic hazard, but the exact event is difficult (if not impossible) to forecast and thereby the computation of expected losses would be just a rough estimation. Depending on the attitude of individual in front of risk, the responses can vary from "*maximax strategy*" in a risk-prone person to a more preventive approach of "*minimax strategy*" or "*regret minimization*" in risk-adverse people in line with the "precautionary principle". This is, hence, a situation of uncertainty, where not only the exact impact of a policy is known in advance but the probability of the different results is also unknown (Martínez Alier and Roca Jusmet, 2006).

Fire risk reduction encompasses manifold contemporary effects which are located in diverse zones. Reduced fire impact affects *in-situ* beneficiaries: decreases forest vulnerability for a forest manager or diminishes exposure of a house owner. Reduced easiness of fire propagation influences the surrounding holdings, what has been termed as "adjacency externalities" in Crowley et al (2009) e.g. benefiting neighbouring landowner. Reduced severity decreases potential erosion affects to downstream land users (e.g. farmers). Reduced fire occurrence implies landscape maintenance, which affects to all located in the visual basin (e.g. nice views in rural tourism establishments); mere forest preservation also concerns all those assigning an existence value. Forest maintenance is also related to other multiple services such as water quantity and quality provision, CO₂ sequestration, biodiversity safeguarding, etc. For any of these impacts, **excludability** is difficult, allowing for free-riders: regardless of individual contribution to prevention all agents will in any case benefit from a reduced risk. This discourages individual investments towards a reduced risk: e.g. a forest owner will not face motivation to cover the full effort of reducing surface biomass if as an external consequence this diminishes neighbours' risk while they are not contributing. External effects may become secondary when the beneficiary perceived that welfare increase due to preventive measures exceeds devoted efforts. In this line some agents may conduct in their own interest fire preventing measures, such as forest owners whose expected revenues from market products cover the expenses, or local volunteers whose efforts are rewarded by the feeling of contributing the morally positive task of protecting their local environment. In any case, if existing individual efforts for fire prevention, they would tend to be lower than what could be socially desirable.

In terms of **rivalry**, apparently the fact that one person benefits from reduced fire risk does not subtract others to also benefit from such reduction. Hence, as consumptive use of the service does not preclude others to do so, then it would be considered a **public good**. How much each one must contribute to financing this public good is a crucial question. As Samuelson (1954) notes that "no decentralized pricing system can serve to determine optimally these levels of collective consumption", calling for government intervention for public good provision.

There is, however, some discussion on the **potential congestion** nature of fire protection. Ostrom and Ostrom (1977) point out that "*few, if any, joint consumption goods are perfectly nonsubtractible (...) Fire protection, another joint consumption good, may deteriorate when a finite force experiences a high rate of demand. Such goods are then subject to degradation or erosion in their quality unless supply is modified to meet the new demand*". They classify "fire protection" under "public good". Brueckner (1981) develops a model considering fire protection as a congested public good, finding that congestion properties are close to those of a pure public good. He mainly refers to

congestion as provoked by increasing population, what augments overall people's exposure in form of e.g. more urbanisations being built, and hence more fire protection is demanded. Here he assimilates fire protection as "fire suppression capability", related to water supply. We find that here authors refer to "congestion" in the public service provision, understood as the reduction in per capita protective measures when population increases due to limited public budget. Such potential rivalry in use of public means responds to the opportunity costs of public budget, what is shared for almost any other type of prototypical public good. This may be the result from confounding the good with the financial resources devoted to get it: perhaps fire protection is more costly the more people are benefited, but once ensured a protection level, its enjoyment does not depend on the number of beneficiaries.

In general we can consider fire risk as a **public bad**, and hence its reduction as a public bad prevention. Both, provision of a public good and prevention of a public bad should be equivalent in strategic terms (Sonemanns et al, 1998). Ostrom and Ostrom (1977) remarked the fact that agents have little choice opportunities both in deciding the amount of public good to consume and on the quality of the good itself. Yet, the structure of institutional arrangements may have some effect on the degree of choice that individuals have. These authors also noted that in some cases, public good supply is affected by the fact that users of services also function as essential co-producers. Explicitly, they mention "*the efforts of citizens to prevent fires and to provide early warning services when fires do break out are essential factors in the supply of fire protection services*" (p.20). Hence, such institutional arrangements should take into account the possibilities of beneficiaries' contribution. This is especially relevant in the case of analysing possibilities to implement PES schemes over public goods, whose rationale induces beneficiaries to financially engage in ensuring the provision of those goods. In the following section we will discuss about beneficiaries' involvement and potentiality of collective action in public good provision.

3. Analytical framework for collective responses to environmental resources management

3.1. Principles of collective governance for environmental resources

Ostrom (1990, cited in Becker and Ostrom, 1995) analysed CPR cases with successful natural resources management, what she considers "robust institutions", understanding as such those meta rules systems that outline resource systems and institutions that have survived over long periods of time (Becker and Ostrom, 1995). The careful observation of those robust cases showed common features that were not occurring in unsuccessful cases. Hence, Ostrom (1990) listed seven "design principles" (box 1) that tend to characterise durable management of CPR. Hardin's predictions would be likely in cases where those principles are not accomplished in a sufficient level.

Box 1. Design principles for durable common-pool resources (Source: Ostrom, 1990)

1. Clear defined boundaries: who and what can benefit from the common-pool resource?
2. Proportional equivalence between benefits and costs: benefits derived from the common-pool resource must relate to the inputs each beneficiary imposes
3. Collective-choice arrangements: affected users participate in defining rules
4. Monitoring: auditor and accountability to users
5. Graduated sanctions: non-accomplishment consequences
6. Conflict resolution mechanisms: rapid and low-cost access to disagreements among users of users-officials
7. Minimal recognition of rights to organise: external institutions do not challenge the decisions and there are long-term tenure rights.

Drawing upon Ostrom (1990) design principles, Dietz et al (2003) extract the general principles for robust governance institutions of environmental resources, three of them being especially relevant for large scales, whereas the rest apply in localized resources (Figure). These authors acknowledge, however, that few settings in the world are characterized by all of these conditions.

Figure - General principles for robust governance of environmental resources (green, left and right columns) and the governance requirements they help meet (yellow, center column). Each principle is relevant for meeting several requirements. Arrows indicate some of the most likely connections between principles and requirements. Principles in the right column may be particularly relevant for global and regional problems. Source: Dietz et al (2003).

A model that resumes the sufficient conditions for a sustainable CPR has been the goal for many scholars (Agrawal, 2003). Agrawal (2003) calls for a more biophysically sophisticated approach to Ostrom (1990) model. He compiles the results from other commons scholars, drafting a list of critical features on common-pool resources that facilitate the sustainable use of the resource. It is composed by a block of resource characteristics, a block on the features of the relevant group of people (we will consider here beneficiaries and providers, if they are different), followed by the relationships between that specific society with the resource and within them (institutional arrangements) and finally, the external context that can affect these agents. From this framework, we have selected the most relevant features for a potential collective prevention of a public bad (box 2). We will refer to:

- “exposed-to-bad group” as those agents whose values are at stake. Values at stake can be private goods and hence affect a relatively small group, or they can be ecosystem services that affect society at large, becoming the group larger;
- “preventive resource” to the inputs required to decrease public bad risk;
- “preventive agents” to those who reduce public bad risk;

Box 2. Critical features for sustainable collective action (based on Agrawal, 2003)

1) Resource system characteristics

- i) Small size and well-defined boundaries: location of preventive resources and frequent bad occurrence
- ii) Possibilities of storage of benefits: persistence of public bad reduced effects
- iii) Predictability: public bad occurrence and resource ecological processes

2) Group characteristics: exposed-to-bad group and preventive agents

- i) Small size and clearly defined boundaries
- ii) Shared norms, homogeneity of identities and interests
- iii) Past successful experiences: “social capital”
- iv) Appropriate leadership, familiar with changing external environments, connected to local traditional elite
- v) Interdependence among agents: e.g. power relationships

(1 and 2) Relationship between resource system characteristics and group characteristics

- i) Overlap between exposed-to-bad group residential location and resource

ii) High levels of dependence by exposed-to-bad group members on the goods under risk and of the preventive agent on the resource system

iii) Fairness in allocation of benefits: protected to preventive agents

iv) high levels of public bad protection demand and gradual change in levels of demand

3) Institutional arrangements among preventive agents and among exposed-to-risk group

i) Rules are simple and easy to understand

ii) Locally devised access and management rules

iii) Ease in enforcement of rules and graduated sanctions

iv) Low transaction costs

v) Accountability

4) External environment

i) Technology:

a) Low-cost preventive technology (financially accessible)

b) Time for adaptation to new technologies related to the public bad problem

ii) External markets

a) Low levels of articulation with external markets

b) Gradual change in articulation with external markets

iii) Demographic changes: relatively stable population

iv) Higher levels of administration

a) Central governments should not undermine local authority

b) Appropriate levels of external aid to compensate local agents for preventive activities

We can find many common points in Agrawal's (2003) model with the broader Socio-Ecological Systems (SES) analytical framework. SESs are defined by Anderies et al. (2004) as "*social systems in which some of the interdependent relationships among humans are mediated through interactions with biophysical and non-human biological units*". A primary interest of scholars focusing on SESs has been examining their ability to sustain themselves in the face of disturbances over time. Design principles from Ostrom (1990) can serve as a starting point for a diagnostic approach to the study of complex SESs (Ostrom and Cox, 2010), which allow also to cope with public good problems.

Applying Ostrom (1990) and Agrawal (2003) model allows for discussing on critical features ensuring the governance of the natural resource. Analysing the effects of the features in management and use of natural resources, it becomes clear that they also could sometimes facilitate public goods' governance: even with government competences to solve certain problems, collective action moved by individuals' interests may complement and hence support government policies. In this line, elements that facilitate self-organisation (group characteristics), rationalisation of resource use (resource system characteristics and relationships resource-group), empowerment of resource user and local managers (conducive external environment) as well as their participation in norm definition and enforcement (institutional arrangements) are likely to contribute to public policies' implementation.

3.2. Focus on economic incentives

Solving Common-Pool Resources dilemmas involves on one hand restricting access and on the other side creating incentives for users to invest in the resource instead of overexploiting it (Ostrom et al. 1999). When they are economic incentives, the question arise on how to finance such measures. In the European policy arena the issue of involving the user and/or beneficiaries of certain natural resources in covering the costs of their provision/maintenance is gaining force in the last years (ForestEurope, 2011). Such would become the basis for the Payment for Environmental Services (PES) mechanisms (Wunder, 2005; Muradian et al., 2010), by which also land managers would commit to provide the demanded goods and services.

The role of government can vary in PES. *Private PES schemes* refer to buyers paying directly to environmental service (ES) provider, this is, agreements are held between private agents and government implication may be reduced to formal contract law enforcement. In *public PES schemes* government acts on behalf of ES beneficiaries, collecting taxes and paying ES providers (Wunder, 2005). In the case of tax-funded programs, voluntary engagement of beneficiaries does not occur, but still providers' participation would be voluntary.

It must be taken into account the results from the experiment conducted by Sonnemans and colleagues (1998): even if from a strategic point of view, the provision of a public good is equivalent to the prevention of a public bad, framing this social dilemma has a noticeable impact on decisions. While deciding whether to provide help to public good or not, subjects act more cooperatively and the public good is provided more often than when the decision is whether to prevent a public bad or not. As a consequence, the emergence of voluntary actions from beneficiaries to prevent a public bad is less likely as well as their willingness to pay would be low. In order to achieve an adequate risk level for the community government intervention may then be required. This reasoning would lead to public PES schemes

3.3. Property rights and Payments for Environmental Services

Property rights constitute an institution that according to Schlager and Ostrom (1992) includes different dimensions, as follows: access, withdrawal/harvesting, management, exclusion and alienation. Diverse agents can play a role in each dimension, respectively: entrant, user, claimant, proprietor or owner (Table). Access and withdrawal represent the “Operational level” rights, entitled to individual resource users; however, management, exclusion and alienation constitute “Collective-choice level” rights, related to the strategic planning over the resource. According to these authors, not everyone can participate in their definition (only those exercising certain authority over the group) and in their implementation (generally those fulfilling certain requirements). Policy instruments towards a sustainable use of natural resources, hence, must look for a coherent and adequate coordination of those agents.

Table - Property rights dimensions and role of involved agents (based on: Schlager and Ostrom, 1992)

	Alienation	Exclusion	Management	Withdrawal	Access
Visitor	X	X	X	X	X
Harvester	X	X	X	X	
Claimant	X	X	X		
Proprietor	X	X			
Owner	X				

Scholars that have focused in the institutional aspects of PES have pointed out the relevance of property rights in their design and implementation (Corbera et al, 2009; Swallow et al, 2005). In fact, designing and implementing a PES scheme entails a redistribution of property rights in a way that those goods one was benefiting from/using free of charge, now it has to be paid/compensated. That those markets for ES did not exist before necessarily means that there have previously been some obstacles to the operation of those markets (Swallow et al, 2005). Such reshaping of rights may collude with pre-existing governance systems, challenging perceived rights and duties over natural resources, with a potential problem of environmental justice.

RESEARCH QUESTION and METHODOLOGY

In this study we try to elucidate which are the feasibility conditions for a private PES scheme to emerge from collective action to provide a public good (a public bad prevention, in this case); and secondly, which would be the required government intervention.

For this purpose we analyse diverse property rights and institutional contexts (case studies) that may shape the potential collective action and incentive schemes that promote the procurement of fire prevention. We assume fire occurrence as fixed and extinction means to have achieved a maximum limit. We focus on the role of pastures as a preventive measure and the possibilities of collective responses and government role in them.

A first review of existing scholars’ literature on commons has provided the basis on critical features on sustainable management of collective consumption resources. Those have been contrasted with the available legal and scientific documentation on existing case studies of incentives for herders, as providers of the fire prevention service. Case

studies have not been purposively selected, but instead they have emerged after an exploratory search of available examples in Spain. They cover different incentive schemes in Mediterranean-type forests, where pastures are often not fenced (hence, apparently of open access), and wildfire appears as a collective problem, as follows:

- compensatory payments to herders for pasturing in fuelbreak areas in the Valencian region (Eastern Spain), in view of maintaining fire prevention infrastructures;
- public contracts with shepherds in Andalusian mountains (Southern Spain) for maintaining low biomass in strategic areas for fire prevention;
- agreements between the regional forest administration of Catalonia (North-eastern Spain) with some herders for maintaining low biomass in public forests;
- agreements between private forest owners with herders in Catalonia for maintaining low forest understory;
- service contracts between some Catalan municipalities and shepherds to maintain low biomass in the security perimeter of urbanisations in the interface with forests;
- specific agro-environmental grants for herders in Catalonia for pasturing forest understorey in fire-strategic areas.

So far, research on these cases has been focused on the ecological impacts of grazing, and few in a comparative economic analysis of the alternatives for wildfires prevention measures. Some of these studies have already pointed out some socio-economic impacts achieved, which in some cases were also secondary or non-written objectives, very relevant in terms of rural behaviour and long-term maintenance of the resource. In order to complement available literature with the property right dimensions, schemes implementation and social perceptions of the CPR under focus, a questionnaire was designed based on the critical principles compiled by Agrawal (2003) and the dimensions of Schlager and Ostrom (1992). The questionnaire had an introductory set of questions about grazing rights and basic data on the sector and about the fire prevention measures in place. It was followed by a Delphi-type table with 30 statements, with which respondent should “completely agree”, “agree”, “disagree” or “completely disagree”. Each statement also included an option of “don’t know/don’t reply” for those points unknown for respondents, and a space for comments, asking them to justify the answer given if deemed appropriate. These open contributions have enriched the analysis. A total of 24 questionnaires to stakeholders (technicians, researchers and representatives of forest owners and herders) of each case were sent during summer 2012, being returned 14. A basic simple frequencies analysis of the replies has been conducted, mainly looking for convergences either in a block of replies supporting the sentences (“agree” and “totally agree”) or those rejecting the statements (“disagree” and “totally disagree”). A summary of the questions and frequencies is available in Annex 1. No second round of questionnaires has been sent due to the high convergence rate of the gathered replies. In order to respect anonymity of respondents, references to comments provided count with a codification: a letter indicating the initial of their case study area, followed a number corresponding to the individual. The compiled information allows for a comparative analysis among different systems, giving some light on the critical features. In addition, an attempt to construct a model has been drafted (annex 2) in order to structure agents and their variables, and how the programs have affected them.

RESULTS

This chapter is organised as follows: (i) an overview of the grazing activity is provided, what facilitates the understanding of each case’s specific problematic; (ii) a description of each incentive scheme; (iii) a description of the property right dimensions of forest goods in the case study regions; and (iv) and brief analysis of the incentives.

1. The pastoral activity

The main objective of pastoralism is the production of animal-derived products for human consumption. The activity takes place as follows:

1. A herder (*pastor*) breeds the animals extensively by bringing them to open air pastures areas. When the owner of the animals (*ganadero*) is a different person, the herder is contracted (in more or less formal way) and in charge of implementing the field work. Otherwise he also decides on the strategic issues: production objectives: either wool, leather, milk or meat; product trading, generally negotiating with an intermediary; and according to environmental restrictions imposed, s/he also decides on the technology of production to be used: animal's race, number of heads, type of feeding, seasonal distribution of activities, vaccination and reproduction means, etc.
2. The herder finds the appropriate place for implementing the breeding, leads the animals there, and routinely oversees them controlling their feeding and growth. Animals can feed from self-owned pastures, from communal pastures or from externals (a private individual, a municipality or the state). In this last case, the herder needs the consent of the landowner. To get that permission, the shepherd may incur in some grazing fees. In publicly owned areas, the managing agency can open a call to assign grazing contracts, usually entailing a deposit and a payment per area. Grazing allowance can last for one or more seasons. Landowners can establish certain conditions on where and how to pasture. Given the temporal character of the contract, landowner does usually take care of providing and maintaining the required fixed infrastructure: water points, fences or refuges.
3. Herders' time consumption largely varies according to the animal in focus: fences are usually more effective with big cattle (horses and cows), needing less surveillance, while small cattle may require full time control, often with dogs. In this last case, pasturing becomes the only source of income for shepherds and limits leisure time.
4. Animals' plant consumption varies across species, being goats able to breed from the least palatable species, these are, the dry, hart and thorny plants. This only happens, however, when goats do not have alternative easier species to eat. Water availability is also a crucial point, especially for the larger need of the big cattle. In addition, resting places do determine the mobility possibilities of the flocks.

Pasturing as a fire prevention measure

Moving from a scenario with high surface biomass (shrubs and those bushes connecting herbs with the lowest branches from trees) to a situation with lower biomass can help in achieving the last three objectives of fire prevention (Table). Fuel reduction projects in forests are intended to reduce fire risk by reducing surface fuels, continuity of fuels from the surface to the canopy, and continuity of fuels within the canopy. Ignition probability is unaffected, but if a fire does occur, fire intensity and effects on the understorey may be lower owing to the lesser fuel loading (Keeley et al, 2009).

Experts coincide that this intense fuel reduction is neither necessary nor desirable to happen all over the territory, but mainly in selected "strategic areas": e.g. those with a predominant wind, with a historical recurrence of fires, or near human settlements or valuable places. Biomass reduction can be operationalised either by mechanical means (e.g. brushcutter, bulldozers or skidders) or other more close-to-nature means (old agriculture parcel cultivation, manual collection of fuel wood or pasturing). Recognising grazing as an effective tool for risk reduction in Spain is a novel approach and has been acknowledged as such in recent forums, not only within the pastoral community -see conclusions of the "*Guardabosc*" meeting (FMR and CaixaCatalunya, 2010)- but also within the fire extinction sector -see conclusions of the IVth National Symposium on Forest Fires (2011)-. Russi et al (2010) identified silvo-pastoralism programs for fire prevention as potential PES schemes in Catalonia.

Pastures: challenges

In the Northern Mediterranean rim (with the exception of some Balkan countries), urbanisation of society, technological changes in livestock breeding and market evolution of cattle products have lead to a significant decrease of the pastoral activity. There are less people interested in becoming a herder, and those who would like to do so often find barriers due to their non-rural origin, limited experience or lack of available land. Recently some

initiatives have emerged in this line, facilitating the training - such as the recent Herders' school in Catalonia³ and Andalucía- or temporal land management contracts -land banks in Galicia (Onega et al, 2010) and an incipient similar initiative in Catalonia (XCT, 2012)-. In Spain most of the normative is established at the regional government level. In all cases, grazing in private pastures requires landowners' permission, while grazing in public forests is regulated as public-domain good of privative use against a license or concessions.

2. Incentive schemes in focus

2.a. Payments for shepherds in firebreaks in Comunidad Valenciana (VAL)

From 1996 to 2009, the Government of the Valencian community –located in eastern of Spain- launched open calls⁴ for firebreaks maintenance in either public, communal or private forests by means of controlled grazing. Pastures assignments prioritised those herders participating in past editions with positive results, and those in critical areas for fire prevention, as determined by the Government. Herders received a basic compensation payment of 22€/ha.yr, what could be increased in around 20€/ha if fencing and establishment of water points are needed. Eligible shepherds were those that had the grazing rights on a specific area and count with a pasture plan. Eligible animals were sheep, goat and bovine cattle. The required commitment from shepherds was a minimum number of animals in the selected areas during a minimum of days in the winter-spring and autumn seasons. Control was executed by technicians from the administration. In addition there was a scientific monitoring of the impacts (Dopazo González et al, 2009) and its economic benefits in terms of avoided costs (Dopazo González et al, 2012). According to the published resolutions of the last call⁵, 60 shepherds were selected covering a total over 2600ha of grazing mainly with sheep. The total eligible cost at that time was 79000€, being possible to prorate when applicants exceed the available budget.

2.b. Payments for shepherds in firebreaks in Andalucía (AND)

In Andalucía, located in southern Spain, livestock grazing of fuelbreaks started being tested in 2003 and remuneration for shepherds was implemented in 2007 (Ruiz-Mirazo, 2011). Payments currently range from 42 to 90€/ha, according to a formula with variables of grazing difficulty (steepness, type of vegetation and distance to animal housing) associated to the fuelbreaks and actual accomplishment (Varela-Redondo et al, 2007). As in the Valencian case, officials from the administration control the fuel reduced. Simultaneously a scientific follow-up of the impacts is conducted. The selection of participating shepherds is done through an individual assessment of proposals by forest officials and other stakeholders. Another difference with the system in Valencia is that although there are also subsidies for fuel reduction in private forests, they are not coordinated within the regional fuelbreak network RAPCA⁶. By 2010, this Andalusia scheme reached a total surface of 2.202 ha, which were grazed mainly by goats and sheep, with 67 participating shepherds (Ruiz-Mirazo, 2011), being increased in 2012 up to 222 shepherds covering 6.700ha (Ruiz-Mirazo, 2012).

2.c. Multiplicity of initiatives in Catalonia

Located in the north-east of Spain, Catalonia counts with a portfolio of initiatives regarding controlled grazing. Some of them are punctual in place and time: goats promoted by the Forest Defence Group of Penedés-Garraf in Subirats (FADFPG, 2012); donkeys and cows in the Gavarres range, promoted by a the private-public landowners' Consortium of the Gavarres in (Besalú et al, 2011); a herder contract within the transnational fire prevention project PRINCALB

³ Projecte Grípià. Territori Ramader: <http://projectegripia.wordpress.com>

⁴ DOGV (2009-1). Ordre d'11 de maig de 2009, per la qual es convoquen i s'aproven les bases reguladores de les ajudes gestionades per la Direcció General de Gestió del Medi Natural, en matèria de prevenció d'incendis forestals, per a l'exercici 2009. Conselleria de Medi Ambient Aigua Urbanisme i Habitatge.

⁵ DOGV (2009-2). Resolució de 13 d'agost de 2009, de la Conselleria de Medi Ambient, Aigua, Urbanisme i Habitatge, per la qual es resol la convocatòria de primes compensatòries destinades al control de les pastures i el matollar a àrees tallafocs de la Comunitat Valenciana. Conselleria de Medi Ambient, Aigua, Urbanisme i Habitatge.

⁶ RAPCA: Red de Áreas Pasto-Cortafuegos de Andalucía

France-Spain in L'Albera protected area in 2009⁷. In the following sections we will focus in the most extended schemes, relevant by their design and more durable in time.

2.c.1. Economic agreement Shepherds' Federation - Regional government (CAT1)

Motivated by a visit to the Valencian experience, the Catalan Federation of Sheep and Goat Associations (FECOC) proposed and signed in 2000 an agreement with the regional public agency, by which 5 shepherds conduct maintenance of fire breaks or low fuel density areas previously cleaned by mechanical means. Besalú et al (2011) report that in 2001 a pilot project starts in Montmell range, being extended in 2004 to the protected areas of Montgrí and Poblet, all properties of the regional government. Like the case in Andalucía, there is no specific open call and the initial shepherds are still participating today, receiving an average of 40€/ha.yr. Shepherds are located respectively in Poblet Mountains, Montmell range, Cabra de Camp and Montgrí natural park (2). Official sources report 4.245ha under controlled grazing (DAAM, 2012a). There is a scientific follow-up (Baiges et al, 2007; Vives et al, 2012).

2.c.2. Municipal contracts with shepherds for urbanisations' perimeters maintenance (CAT2)

Each autonomous community under study has contemplated in its legislation the risky situation of urbanisations in the wildland-urban interface (WUI). Andalucía obliges⁸ urbanisation landowners to elaborate a "Self-protection plan", which will include measures for prevention and extinction of fires. Planning relies on the owner, supervision and watching over its implementation on the municipality. Valencia establishes⁹ the indications for security perimeters (minimum width of 25m, increasing with dominant wind) as well as other accessibility and water points. Again, the final responsible of implementation is not specified. Catalonia experienced the inaction from similar normative, hence passing a law¹⁰ which creates servitude on the affected perimeter, and complements similar technical requirements by specifying the municipality as subsidiary responsible, which also receives the right to charge the affected neighbours for the service.

As a consequence some consistories –to my knowledge only in Girona, Matadepera, Begues, Sant Boí del Llobregat and Sant Pere de Vilamajor- have engaged in programmes of controlled grazing around urbanisations. This system results cheaper than the alternatives, but sometimes they receive complaint from residents if those are of urban origin, not accustomed to animals' transit. There is no systematic register of this type of contracts, neither are the paid amounts publicly available. Some of these initiatives have been encouraged by the FDG of the municipalities (e.g. FDG Matadepera, FDG St.Boí). A catastrophic fire event may be behind the initiative, such as the one in Matadepera in 2003 (Otero, 2011). Formal agreements may be through municipal subsidy to the FDG who will contract the herder (e.g. Matadepera) or direct service contract from the municipality (e.g. Sant Boí, Girona).

2.c.3. Agreements between forest owners and shepherds to reduce fuel load (CAT3)

Since 2004 a relevant savings bank foundation (Obra Social de Caixa Catalunya) started funding initiatives of controlled grazing, with a pilot action in their own Alinyà holding, followed by actions in other locations in Catalonia. All these actions were coordinated since 2009 under the umbrella of the denominated "forest guard" (*Guardabosc*) project¹¹.

⁷ Web PRINCALB project:

<http://www20.gencat.cat/portal/site/DAR/menuitem.3645c709047c363053b88e10b031e1a0/?vgnextoid=de080e9b2e203310VgnVCM2000009b0c1e0aRCRD&vgnnextchannel=de080e9b2e203310VgnVCM2000009b0c1e0aRCRD&vgnnextfmt=default>

⁸ BOJA (1999). Law 5/99 de Prevención y Lucha contra los Incendios Forestales. And BOJA (2001) Decree 144/2001 de 13 de noviembre, por el que se aprueba el Reglamento de Prevención y Lucha contra los Incendios Forestales

⁹ DOGV (2007). Decree 36/2007 that modifies Decree 67/2006 que aprueba el Reglamento de Planificación y Gestión Urbanística y Territorial.

¹⁰ DOGC (2003) Law 5/2003, de mesures de prevenció d'incendis forestals en les urbanitzacions sense continuïtat immediata amb la trama urbana

¹¹ "Caixa Catalunya aboga per recuperar rouredes i alzinars per prevenir els incendis forestals". Press release. 04/08/2009.

http://obrasocial.catalunyacaixa.com/osocial/idiomes/1/premsa/agost_prevencioincendis_comarquescentrals.pdf

The main characteristic of these initiatives is the private-private character of the participants, this is, the direct agreement between forest owner and the shepherd, framed in the denominated "land stewardship agreements". In some cases, these agreements also entail remuneration to the shepherd. The foundation support was punctual and devoted for the start-up of the activities.

In this line, the provincial government of Barcelona also financially supported a decentralised programme with forest owners associations. The particular case of Castelltallat deserves attention, as being a non-monetary exchange agreement. Castelltallat Mountains, in the Central depression of Catalonia, have been severely castigated by forest fires in the last years, the largest in 1998 and two smaller ones until today. The affected forest owners have become especially aware about this hazard and catalysed by the provincial fire prevention service, an association was established in view of improving regeneration. The "social capital" created has encouraged this group of owners to engage in innovative approaches, such as the suggestion of releasing shepherds for paying grazing rights in exchange of a reduction of surface biomass by their cattle. Preliminary studies on the pastoral potential of the area, as well as of the strategic points from the fire point of view highlighted the adequate technical conditions. Contacts between local shepherds and forest owners were facilitated, resulting in 2009/2010 in land stewardship agreements between the forest owners' association and individual shepherds. By January 2011, 30 forest owners have signed the agreements with 37 shepherds, covering an area of 3.160ha, with an estimated "fire resistant area" of 7.200ha and significant reductions in terms of fire prevention costs when compared to the alternatives of prescribed burning or mechanical brush removals (Pauné and Estaqué, 2011). Participant shepherds can also apply for the CAP grants (Besalú et al, 2011).

Similar negotiations are being held in Montserrat Natural Park (a protected area near the metropolitan region of Barcelona). In these cases, the public administration has acted as catalyser of the agreements, has promoted preliminary studies and implementation follow-up. These donations are generally of punctual nature, provided the availability of budget; hence managers attempt to channel this financing towards long-term, expensive actions, mainly infrastructure provision. Studies show that maintenance of those systems and agreements are sensibly lower (Pauné and Estaqué, 2011).

2.c.3. Agro-environmental measure: grazing in Priority Protection Perimeters (CAT4)

The coupling between farming practices and environmental protection constitutes a primary objective of the European CAP, particularly since the first agro-environmental measures were implemented in 1992 (Ruiz-Mirazo, 2011). The grazing management of fuelbreaks being a good example of this, it has long been funded by this European programme in south-eastern France (Thavaud, 2006).

The Rural Development Programme 2007-2013 in Catalonia includes an agro-environmental measure (Axis 2, measure 214, action 21407) to promote understorey grazing within the Priority Protection Perimeters (PPP). PPP are large forest areas with high fire risk¹². Such activity can receive a subsidy from the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), which is 75% financed by European funds. Applicants' commitments consists of a minimum of 15ha grazed, to be maintained with animals during at least 4 months, and maintain the stockbreeding activity during 5 years more, fencing the area and construct the required water points. Rewards depend on the type of animals prorated by the area, ranging from 61 EUR/ha (goats), 66 EUR/ha (cows) up to 74 EUR/ha (sheep) if the grazed area is of 50ha. The established objective for such action is to reach the 30 shepherds covering an area of 5000ha (DAAR, 2006). This written goal is far lower than the total PPP area of 1.130.000ha in Catalonia (DAAM, 2012b); from this fact and also the limited budget assigned (54.000 EUR) and the restriction to spread to new areas it can be deduced that this is only a complementary funding of the entire PPP network maintenance. So far 70 rangers have benefited from this

¹² DOGC (2011). Ordre AAM/22/2011, de 3 de febrer, per la qual s'aproven les bases reguladores dels ajuts associats al contracte global d'explotació, i es convoquen els corresponents a l'any 2011. Departament d'Agricultura, Ramaderia, Pesca, Alimentació i Medi Natural

measure. Established requirements (registered soil use, slopes and preliminary silvicultural treatments) limit participants' eligibility.

Table – Summary of incentive schemes in the case study areas.

Name of the programme, Place	AND Firebreaks maintenance payment to shepherds in Andalucía	CAT 1 Low biomass areas maintenance agreement with federation of herders, Catalonia	CAT 2 Municipal service of WUI maintenance, Catalonia	CAT 3 Forest owner – herder agreement, Catalonia	CAT 4 Agro-environmental measure for understorey grazing in PPP, Catalonia	VAL Firebreaks maintenance payments to shepherds in Valencia
Type of initiative	Service contract payments to shepherds for fire-preventing pasturing	Contract regional government - herder	Service contract municipal government - herder	Formal or informal agreement between forest owner and herders (in line with land stewardship agreements)	Global Exploitation Contract (framework contract) and specific grant agreement	Specific grant agreement
Herder's commitment	intensive grazing in strategic lines (firebreaks and low fuel areas)	intensive grazing in strategic lines (usually firebreaks)	intensive grazing around buildings, 25m buffer area	intensive grazing in strategic forest zones	intensive grazing in strategic lines (PPP)	intensive grazing in firebreaks
Amount interchanged	Formula (variables: area, difficulty & intensity, accomplishment): 33-70€/ha.yr	Around 40 €/ha.yr Compatible with other economic incentives both for forest owner and shepherd.	Not published. Report a cost for the municipality around 400€/ha.yr.	In kind agreements, exempted pasture fees for grazing rights in compensation for biomass reduction.	From 61-70 €/ha.yr if 50ha (prorating otherwise). Compatible with other economic incentives.	Average of 40 €/ha.year
Payer	Government of Andalucía (intermediary: public forest enterprise)	Catalan government (intermediary: herders' association)	Municipal government (no intermediary)	Forest owners (lost revenue) Punctual contribution from external donors.	Government of Catalonia through European funds	Valencian Government (no intermediary)
Timing	Since 2007.	Since 2001-2 (approx).	Since 2007-08 (approx).	Since 2010 (approx.)		1994-2009. Stopped because of crisis.

3. Property rights dimensions

Table compiles rights dimensions according to the agents that can enjoy them. It allows for differentiating the peculiarities in each region. Hence, we find that Catalonia is the only case study with communal forests classified as such, this is, private ownership of a group; they are mainly around forested settlements in the Pyrenees. Valencian community also counts with communal-owned forests, mainly the so-called *boalars* or *devesas boyales* in the province of Castelló, which were mainly used for pastoral use; however due to the “Desamortización” process in the 19 century they ended up in municipal ownership with recognised rights for the neighbours. Today their alienation and management rights rely in the city hall, whereas access and harvesting in its citizens. Similar situation occurs in Andalucía with the *montes de propios*. Some of these still conserve their ancient customary arrangements. However, their current management rights would need a different study. A recent study has identified existing underperformance factors of the communal forests in Catalonia and provides suggestions for their improvement (Placència et al, 2012). Pastures’ organisation in communal areas in Northern rim countries would deserve a separate study, but in any case government intervention is limited by law as in any other private holding, being possible that ancient structures of self-management apply.

Concerning fire management: while Valencian and Catalanian governments themselves take care of fire prevention planning at the regional level, Andalusia undertake such planning only in public forests, allowing private forest owners to organise their own holding prevention plan. In order to promote those contingency plans, the Andalusian government offers regular subsidies for the planning and its execution¹³. The government in all regions is responsible of the execution of the fire preventive activities in forests managed by its forest agency, but usually also assumes the related expenses for municipalities and to certain extent also those of private forests.

All three regions have issued norms indicating requiring buildings located in the wildland-urban interface (WUI) to maintain security perimeters. Only Catalonia has explicitly mentioned the responsibility over the municipality.

In some cases firemen, forest management and contact to stockbreeders depend on a different departments (interior, environment and agriculture, respectively, if this is the case). This structure varies with the periodical governmental reorganisations. It is interesting noting that if all belong to the same body, with a unique budget, it would internalise the benefits of shepherds as reducers of preventive action and of extinction costs. There is, however, a long tradition of department sectoralisation, obstructing interdisciplinary working groups; this trend is being overcome in the last years, and transversal problems are more often faced by multidisciplinary teams. In this way, the call for the (CAT4) agro-environmental measure for grazing in PPP was prepared by a mixed group of foresters, firemen and agronomists when they were separated, and it is in practice channelled through the Agricultural service.

There is a difference between the owner of the animals (*ganadero*) and the person that brings them to pasture in the field (*pastor*), what in some cases may coincide, e.g. typically in Andalucía. Only the exploitation owner is eligible for the agro-environmental measure in Catalonia (CAT4), while the Valencian initiative explicitly detailed the applicant requirement as “the person who brings the herd”. In direct contracts and agreements (AND, CAT2 and CAT3), it seems preferred negotiating and signing with the person who actually brings the flock to the fuelbreak, most likely due to a higher incentive to participate avoiding an intermediary as well as due to a higher compliance. In the first Catalan case (CAT1), there is an interlocutor who was more familiar to herders.

¹³ BOJA (2011). Orden de 19 de diciembre de 2011, por la que se establecen las bases reguladoras de la concesión de ayudas para la Prevención y Control de los Incendios Forestales, en el ámbito de la Comunidad Autónoma de Andalucía, y se efectúa la convocatoria para el año 2012. Consejería de Medio Ambiente de Andalucía.

The degree of municipality implication varies from region to region. Andalucía and Catalonia have issued a normative that frames the local volunteer organisations around wildfires, the denominated Forest Defence Groups (FDG¹⁴¹⁵). Whereas Andalucía contemplates the voluntary participation of municipalities in them, municipal participation constitutes a pre-requisite for the establishment of a FDG in Catalonia. FDG are rather active in Catalonia (depending on the municipality) and not only support firemen in extinction, but also conduct preventive activities in some cases. In Andalucía they are less developed and are mostly focused in extinction. Valencia has no specific legislation and in fact only few cases do exist with local volunteers (in Enguera and Ayora) mainly for fire extinction, but it counts with a long lasting program of fire surveillance volunteers during the summer. The fact that municipal officials have an obliged relation with local field volunteers in prevention does provide a platform of potential discussions on wildfires in general and methods of prevention in particular. In fact, some of the municipal examples in Catalonia have been largely bolstered by the FDG.

Other actors not explicitly mentioned in the table are private donors and foundations. In a few cases, there may be sufficient social awareness to give funds for implementing controlled pastoralism systems. This may be the case of the “*Guardabosc*” project, financed by a well-known foundation of a savings’ bank in Catalonia, who helped launching the CAT3. The motivation of this foundation is rooted in the self-experience of fire prevention in their forest holdings, expanding later the idea of private-private agreements to other locations. With the big fires of this last summer 2012, a new initiative has been launched: “*un català, una cabra*”¹⁶, with no clear achievements yet, but with the aim of promoting extensive grazing.

¹⁴ DOGC (1986). Ordre del 6 d’octubre, sobre regulació de les Agrupacions de Defensa Forestal (ADF). Departament d’Agricultura, Ramaderia i Pesca.

¹⁵ BOJA, (1997). Decreto 208/1997, de 9 de septiembre, por el que se aprueba el Reglamento Forestal de Andalucía.

¹⁶ Web: <http://1catala1cabra.wordpress.com/>

Table - Property rights dimensions in pastures by agents within forest areas in the case study regions: AND: Andalucía; CAT: Catalonia; VAL: Valencian community.

Agent	Rights	
<p>Herder (<i>pastor, cesionario de régimen de pensión del Ganado, se ocupa de pastoreo, cuidado y cría hasta el cebo – DMAH, 2009</i>) <u>Assets</u>: own time, effort, experience and abilities, animals (if owner, <i>ganadero</i>) and corral <u>Technical limits</u>: experts estimate approx. 400 ha or 1000 animals, complement with other pastures and fodder. Depending on the animal type and available infrastructure, mobility is reduced to 5-30km.</p>	Access:	<p>In publicly managed forests: concession contract needed, obtained through auction or open call, usually cheaper and for longer term than private pastures</p> <p>In privately managed forests: needed permission against payment of pasture's rental, generally annual agreements</p> <p>In communal forests: free if registered in the town, and sometimes by drawing lots (<i>suertes</i>) or other local procedure</p>
	Harvest:	<p>In publicly managed forest: established in the concession contract/pastures' plan</p> <p>In privately managed forest: grazing quota and period negotiated and established in the pastures' plan (if existing)</p> <p>In communal forests (only in CAT): locally agreed grazing quota and period</p>
	Management decision power:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participate or not in the programme in VAL, AND, CAT1, CAT2 and CAT3 (only in CAT4 if exploitation titular). Place and area to cover. Directly under supervision of forest guards. - Technical process: herder does day-to-day work, deciding on number and distribution of grazing days, animals' control, mobility; animals' owner decides on strategic issues: product, number and type of animals and complementary food. - To delegate the pasturing by contracting a herder - Participate as trainer in training projects (e.g. Shepherds' School in AND or CAT) - Ask for other subsidies: e.g. agro-environmental measures for autochthonous races in CAT
	Alienation:	Buyer and price of cattle product
<p>Private forest landowner (<i>propietario forestal, del bosque</i>) Landowner can also own cattle and pasture animals; in this case the limits and decision power from the other two apply. <u>Assets</u>: forest area with its content (trees, shrubs and herbs), and the infrastructure <u>Technical limits</u>: expertise and knowledge in forestry, relationship level with shepherds.</p> <p>AND: 73% (those of communal use or <i>monte de propios</i> mixed with municipal statistics) CAT: 75% (and 5% communal) VAL: 65% (those of communal use or <i>boalar</i> mixed with municipal statistics)</p>	Access:	S/he can access everywhere in his/her own forest
	Harvest:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - S/he can harvest timber, but mandatorily needs a notification to the forest agency - S/he can give permission to externals for harvesting timber, pastures, pinecones, mushrooms or cork
	Management decision power:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Forest management planning and silvicultural treatments implementation. Sometimes, planning already foresee pastures. - Planning of firebreaks and their maintenance in AND. - Mandatory maintenance of firebreaks planned by administration (VAL) - Participation in subsidies for fuel reduction or firebreaks maintenance (e.g. priority in CAT, specific grants in AND and some time ago in VAL) - Technical process: providing and maintaining fencing infrastructure, water points and refugee buildings. - Accessibility (maintenance of private roads). - Membership to a Forest Owners 'Association or Forest Defence Association (ADF)
	Exclusion:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Everyone's access is allowed in public roads and in easements such as officially recognised grazing paths (<i>vías pecuarias</i>). - Restricted if desired in the rest through signalling and fencing. However, this is not the usual situation. Fencing does usually take place to prevent animals' access either to control big cattle (bovine and equine) or where valuable trees have been recently planted or regenerated, e.g. place with either large cattle pressure, rabbits or ungulates (deer). Fencing is only against people in cases of hunting holdings.
<p>Forest service at regional level (<i>consejería de medio ambiente o con competencias en silvicultura</i>)</p>	Access:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Control that everyone's access is allowed in public roads and in easements in private forests to the public or certain individuals such as officially recognised grazing paths (<i>vías pecuarias</i>). - Generally open access in public forests.
	Harvest:	- Approval of private forest management plan, in order to be eligible for other grants (CAT). No overview of planning in VAL

<p>Assets: own regional forests and concerted municipal forests, as well as private “conveniados”</p> <p>Technical limits: available forest guards, expertise and awareness in controlled grazing by technicians and higher decision makers, relationship level with shepherds,</p> <p>AND: 11,7% (State forests) CAT: 5% VAL: 8%</p>		<p>foreseen. No mandatory plans in private forests in AND, only in protected areas and following specific rules.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Control of owner’s permission for harvesting (in practice, only in timber in CAT, AND)
	Management decision power:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Forest management planning and silvicultural treatments implementation in regionally managed forests. - Planning of firebreaks in all forest area (CAT & VAL) and only in publicly managed forests (AND). In CAT they are named “PPP” and when needed intervention in private holdings within the PPP, they are designated as “ZAU”. - Fire prevention, firebreaks’ maintenance in own lands. Possible grants to municipal or private forests for maintenance. - Fire extinction (when there is no specific external agency, like firemen) - Grazing technical conditions: number of grazing days per season, reduction in vegetation, slope, carrying capacities... - Technical process: providing and maintaining fencing infrastructure, water points and refuge buildings. Accessibility
	Exclusion:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possible restrictions to public forest roads in protected areas, to control traffic or in high fire season. - Fencing as like previous cases.
	Alienation:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public domain forests are not subject to alienation. Other public forests can be sold. - Assignment process of timber, pastures, pinecones, mushrooms, cork harvesting rights to a individuals and use fee. - Direct contract with shepherds (AND, CAT2) or association (CAT1) for fuelbreak maintenance and control by guards - Open call for compensatory payments for fuelbreak maintenance and control by forest guards (VAL) - [Agricultural agency] Open call of agro-environmental measure in PPP, and control it (CAT4)
<p>Municipality (<i>ayuntamiento</i>)</p> <p>Assets: own municipal forests, expertise in forest management in the municipal staff</p> <p>Technical limits: expertise in forest management in the municipal council, availability of shepherds in the municipality</p> <p>AND: 15,3% CAT: 15% VAL: 34%</p>	Access:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Usually open access.
	Harvest:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Silvicultural treatments, and sometimes organise them in a forest management plan. - Harvesting timber, pastures, pinecones, mushrooms, cork etc needs owner’s permission
	Management decision power:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Forest management planning and silvicultural treatments implementation, as well as accessibility if own managed roads - Firebreaks or low biomass areas are planned at regional level in AND, CAT (so-called PPP) and VAL. Maintenance is generally covered by regional budget. - Technical process: providing and maintaining fencing infrastructure, water points and refugee buildings. - Municipal fire prevention plan. Responsible of security perimeters in urbanisations in CAT. - Membership of a Municipal Forest Owners’ Association. Membership of the local Forest Defence Association (ADF): voluntary in AND, mandatory in CAT, not existent in VAL.
	Exclusion:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Like in regional-managed forests. There are more examples of regulated public forest road in municipalities in CAT. - Fencing as like previous cases
	Alienation:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public domain forests are not subject to full alienation. Other public forests can be sold. - Transfer management right to forest service: “Concerted forests” (by default in CAT, if no forest engineer contracted) - Allow grazing right to a shepherd: place and area to cover, number and type of animals and rental fee. Auction (AND, VAL) - Contract a shepherd for urbanisations’ security perimeter maintenance (CAT2).

4. Analysis of the incentives

Based on the information compiled and inspired in Brueckner (1981), a basic model has been drafted, distinguishing four different agents, and for each its objective function, budgetary and technical constraints. Finally, there is a brief, intuitive analysis of the effect of programme interventions in each possible control variable. These are available in Annex 2.

The underlying principle behind the Valencian scheme is the compensation for foregone income, and “legally the payment would not be considered as a revenue” (V1). The Andalusian experience attempts similarly to cover *lucrus cesans* by means of establishing “a sufficient attractive amount for shepherds, but low enough to reach the maximum area with the available budget” (A3). The agro-environmental measure (CAT4) has an analogous rationale, by having established the amounts through a report to experts (C1, C2). In all cases, the programs follow the typical Payment for Environmental Services’ scheme, by minimum payment would pay off the foregone incomes experimented by herders in the traditional market -because animals are grazing in more hard conditions-. Such payment should at maximum amount up to the avoided costs to society, what would be the savings in fuelbreak maintenance costs, deducing incurred transaction costs.

Figure - PES rationale of payments to shepherds. Based on Pagiola et al, 2004.

The municipal service contracts (CAT2) with shepherds as well those emerging from the FECOC-DGMN (CAT1) would be framed not only in covering costs but near providing a salary to them. Questionnaires indicate the different economic impact in shepherds, from being the program payment around the 10-15% of total individual revenues (AND) to the 60-80% in the CAT1 and CAT2. In Andalusia (and by the order of magnitude of payments, also in Valencia) participating in the program accounts for a lower part of herder’s work, whereas in these specific cases in Catalonia herders can almost make a living only from fire preventive services. A key question not well studied is the costs that herders incur when participating in the program, and that should be studied in the future in order to compare with the current payments they are receiving.

Finally, the philosophy under the private-private agreements (CAT3) is based again in a win-win strategy, but in this case focused on reducing costs for both sides: production expenses for herders and fire preventive measures for the landowner.

Discussion

We could make a distinction between those initiatives where grazing primary objective is the conservation of environmental services as externalities, and those whose main goal is the protection of private goods. In the first group would be the reduction of biomass in forested areas with no specified marketable value (e.g. initiatives in Valencia, Andalucía or CAT1 and CAT4). However, when grazing is focused on avoiding the loss in buildings or of commercial timber value, only secondarily achieves the maintenance of ecosystem services. The loss in private goods may encourage the emergence of individual action, or even the coordination of those individuals collectively to reach larger scales of protection. Public intervention would be directly justifiable in the first case, whereas in the second only as support for maintaining the externalities or secondary benefits to society. Case studies, however, have shown the coordination difficulties for such collective actions to crystallize, being in practice the role of government very relevant in preventive policies (CAT2 and CAT3).

Even when case studies have not been purposively selected, we find that most of the existing schemes are publicly managed. Government acts as the representative of citizens' interest in preventing the public bad, hence being *public-PES* schemes. Its degree of implication may vary from a top-down approach (AND, VAL, CAT4), where initiative starts from the administration, herders only decide whether to participate and choose among a range of given areas to be grazed and full expenses come from public budget, to a more horizontal collaboration where either herders themselves proposed the initiative to the government (CAT1) or expenses come partially from direct beneficiaries (CAT2). The most private-private case (CAT3) also has counted with punctual funding from the administration, in this case not to cover the overall expenses of the scheme, but instead to facilitate high start-up costs.

1. Resource system characteristics

Resource system characteristics affect the visibility of the public bad problems, and therefore the need of intervention to rationalise their use. Uncertainty and lack of information reduce intrinsic motivations towards investment in prevention measures in general for all risk types. Maps of historical series of fires provide information of spatial occurrence and modern systems of weather forecast and satellite images on vegetation humidity allow for a good daily fire danger prediction and hence having extinction personnel alerted; but still there is uncertainty on where exactly the next fire will take place. Often agents ignore the probability of wildfire occurrence and its potential direct effects in their benefits. In other cases agents may wonder whether is worth devoting certain resources to prevention when the probability of occurrence is low. Myopic decisions can be originated from human limited memory: people located in risky areas with frequent episodes more likely devote resources to implement preventive measures, because they recall some recent catastrophic experience. Examples could be found in seismic areas, flooding plains, hurricane- or fire-prone zones.

On the contrary, pasture ecological processes have been largely studied from scientific (researchers) and empirical (herders and technicians) approaches, being feasible the planning of pastoral management. Uncertain events affecting pastures are mainly climatic conditions of seasons: e.g. the drought of this year 2012, with water points available and lower grass naturally growing, what pushes herders to cover vaster areas for grazing or provide fodder to the animals.

Contrary to other public bad preventive policies (e.g. vaccinations), fire reduced risk cannot be stored: the decreased shrub biomass grows again as part of its natural process, therefore needing successive treatments to keep it in an acceptable level. This type of maintenance activities are a crucial, backstage task that is often unknown for citizens and often not recognised by policy-makers. The struggle of technicians to find the adequate budget for maintaining these structures has stimulated the search for the most efficient manner, in some cases deeming convenient a combination of brushcutting with controlled grazing.

Pastures located in strategic areas for fire prevention do usually count with “well-defined boundaries”, in the sense that herders do identify them in field. These surfaces have had at some point a mechanical intervention for biomass reduction, and if grazing starts before vegetation covers again the area it should be easy to differentiate. Questionnaires have pointed out the excellent field knowledge herders have: *“If you tell them the area, they know where it is”* (V3), otherwise *“they can talk to the environmental official”* (V1) and *“they will provide the needed tools”* (C3), *“with the help of a map if required”* (C4) or *“forest guards will accompany him, several times if necessary”* (A2). Another question is whether the fire risk is easily identifiable by potential beneficiaries: in general society has no accustomed eyes to notice the risk when looking at forests. It is possible, then, that an average citizen is within the boundaries of a fire-prone area and does not detect the risk; as a consequence, no fire prevention measure will be taken as it is not perceived as necessary.

“Predictability” relates the resource dynamics, highlighting resource regeneration process and bottle necks as system resilience. Ecological studies on pastures and animal breeding shed light on their interactions and provided agronomic indications on their management, as well as the complementarities with mechanical interventions. Fire predictability in terms of occurrence and behaviour has been also studied and modelled. However, there is still no definitive study capable to distinguish the effects of grazing in fire management, due to the complex interaction with a large variety of factors. This point is relevant when justifying the measure, whose main effects are defended through empirical field observations by technicians and firemen: *“By my own experience I know, because we have had fires in grazed areas, that fire behaviour is much better for extinction (...) and not only once, but in all cases”* (C3), *“The efficiency of these areas with less biomass and less vertical continuity is difficult to proof but GRAF¹⁷ defend them as a priority measure”* (C2).

2. Group characteristics

Social factors outline the easiness of coordination. In terms of size, herders are a rather limited group, whose members are spread all over the geography, what could difficult communication among them. However, new technologies have changed this panorama, mainly for young herders. Forest owners and WUI buildings’ owners, at the regional level, constitute a more difficult identifiable group and they are a large number; at the local level is still feasible, perhaps with a considerable bureaucratic effort.

Ostrom et al (1999) note that groups of people who can identify one another are more likely than groups of strangers to draw on trust, reciprocity and reputation to develop norms. The experiment conducted by Rege and Telle (2004) finds that revealing each person’s identity and his contribution to the provision of a public good may increase voluntary contributions. Close agents’ location, then, refers to the personal meeting opportunities, which offers spaces for interaction and hence facilitates spontaneous action. Whereas herders are based in a town, forest or WUI urbanisations’ owners may be residents in a different place than herders, or their divergent interests do not assist in creating the required platform. People living in rural areas also indicate the distance between those making decisions from urban contexts: they may not capture the reality in the territory, the possible alternatives and their consequences.

This links to the issue of “interdependence among group members”. Power relationships are clearly established with the strong role of government. As possible improvement, there is a claim for horizontal negotiation processes: *“It is a top-down approach, without a space of empowerment for herders”* (A1); *“if both interlocutors feel like understanding each other, there are no reticence (...). There is a need of new decision-making systems, and young herders have much to say (...) Compliance of acquired commitments depends on if they is a pact between both parts (herder-administration)”* (C4). A more clear dependence is revealed between herders and forest owners and herders and technicians: *“many forest owners have asked me to graze in their forests”* (C4), *“some time ago (when forests*

¹⁷ GRAF: Grups de Reforç d’Actuació Forestal, specialised forest firemen body in Catalonia.

were reduce to minimum) herders were kicked out from our forests, and now (...) we pray them return because we need them” (C3).

Facing the problem of fire prevention requires the coordination of behaviour, values and willingness to pay from different involved agents: those that are beneficiaries, those that plan and manage the resources, those that have the tools for risk reduction and those to make decisions. In many cases, this supposes overcoming old conflicts, accept new paradigms and change habits and expectations. Bottom-up initiatives, as agreements between forest owners or municipalities with herders are largely rooted in “shared values” on risk prevention approaches, helping in compliance. Legitimacy perception of top-down approaches, such as the governmental programs, would be increased if all agents share norms: *“herders were happy that finally common sense was applied in forests” (A3)*. Also in terms of values’ coherence, this *activity-enhancing* payment boosts pro-active conducts: there is an effort rewarded. This vision is better understood and valued in rural environments than the generalised cliché of the *rent-seeker* farmer, originated in the “keeping aside lands” measures of CAP-policy, perceived as “paying for doing nothing”.

Questionnaires have shown that herders do not show problems with “changing external environments”: *“they are fully capable to assume the assigned task, due to their great experience to survive in their environment, all their life long” (C3)*; *“They adapt themselves. And those who do not, is not because they are old, but instead because they (...) want not to lose cattle productivity or to ensure animals’ welfare” (A2)*.

There are divergent responses regarding the existence of an “appropriate leadership” among the herder community. *“It depends on the county: there are leaders that encourage or discourage others” (A1)*; *“the mouth-to-mouth is basic in the rural world for the success of these programs” (V1)*; *“Each herder organises himself by his own without following indications of leaders” (C1)*. No consensus appears also on the role of key people: some people consider that the program may be in risk due to the high dependence on the person that either promoted or extended it, while others consider that a “critical mass” of convinced technicians and beneficiaries has been achieved, hence the issue of continuity of this person does not put in danger the permanence of the initiative. It would be interesting the study of leadership structures in urbanisations’ neighbours associations and other local institutions such municipalities and fire volunteers, in order to see potential linkages and influences to reach a final agreement with herders. “Connections to the local traditional elite” is applied here as the existence of strategic program individuals with ability to influence the community leaders. These agents may facilitate the arrival of innovations, the program expansion and the continuity. Local level governance is not clearly linked to the correct implementation of the program, seen the divergent responses. If any role is to be highlighted, the mayor is identified as relevant as well as the local or county forest guard.

“Social capital” is defined by Ostrom and Ahn (2009) as an attribute of individuals and of their relationships that enhance their ability to solve collective-action problems. Multiple forms of social capital exist, being particularly important for collective action: trustworthiness and networks. At local level such social capital stems from “past successful experiences” and has been found as crucial in some of the studied cases. This supports Ostrom and Ahn (2009) assertion that the social capital that citizens can create by linking with each other, with NGOs, and with governmental actors at diverse levels is essential for effective feedback, learning, and crafting of new and better solutions. Personal knowledge of other experiences somewhere else (e.g. Valencian initiative for Catalans, of French initiative for Andalusians) has facilitated the transfer of know-how. Catastrophic events may have left a profound effect in those having suffered it (e.g. forest owners, urbanisations’ owners, village citizens), promoting the search of measures that help in avoiding a repetition. Former successful collective action activities, such as the FDG in some municipalities, or associationism among forest owners, may help in launching new initiatives. Therefore, private owners’ agreements with herders are more likely to take place in areas with high risk perception, as the case of Castelltallat (CAT3). *“People that have suffered a catastrophe are more sensitive to avoid it happen again” (C5)*. When this awareness can be directed into positive action, perception of coordination nuisances may decrease up to

an acceptable level of negotiation, where the roles change: forest owner is not any longer the one providing the good (land) but instead is the herder the one providing a convenient service for the owner. Even with this large private interest, experts draw attention to the need of some external support for channelling such interest to match with the appropriate herder and to group the owners achieving scale economies in efforts and more coherent landscape-scale fire prevention.

All together could be considered a “reorganisation of the socio-ecological system”, as what Otero (2011) mentions from the experience of a wildfire in a Catalan municipality. Successful previous coordination can result in a more structured and dynamic forest sector: this may be the case of Catalonia in comparison with Andalucía (with a similar forest ownership structure and forest yield potential) or Valencia (distant in profitability terms). Long lasting tradition in collective lobbying has resulted in Catalonia in specific forest agencies and high management planning rates. It is likely that this has influenced a more diverse portfolio of payers for this type of programs.

In order to implement preventive grazing in public-managed forests, several behavioural requirements should be met: society in general (as beneficiaries, with access to all the forest externalities) should understand or at least accept the role of fuelbreaks, the required maintenance efforts and the related costs; public officials (with management and exclusion right) should believe in the effects from grazing and count with a narrow relation with their allied herders; herders (with harvesting right) should appreciate the possibilities and the commitments from preventive grazing and implement them; and policy-makers, as higher body deciding budgetary priorities, should understand the benefits and complementarities of the grazing activity within the portfolio of preventive measures. In private managed forests, the landowner should be aware in grazing effects, reformulate relationships with shepherds as allies (facilitating pasturing allowances and infrastructure), and recalculate expected benefits and expenses according to the current situation. It is likely that when all these agents are aligned, successful governance of the problem may occur, in line of what Becker and Ostrom (1995) define as “robust” institutions. These authors found that beneficiaries of these systems had “*devised their rules by trial and error methods*”, what implies that durable institutions are the result of a long-lasting learning process, until agents do find and agree on how to govern the system. From the compiled facts and opinions it becomes clear that there has not been enough time for maturing these arrangements in the case study areas. Whereas some regions (e.g. France) have strong established tradition on fire-preventive pastures, in Spain regions are either in initial stages of exploring, consolidating or upscaling these types of programs.

3. Relationship between resource system characteristics and group characteristics

This interaction resource system-group of beneficiaries reinforces the motivations for action towards a sustainable use. Ostrom and colleagues (2009) remarked the more likely self-regulation from those that depend on a resource in a large proportion of their livelihood and having some autonomy to make their own rules, because they will perceive benefits easier. However, to coordinate with others they need to share an image on how the resource system operated and how their actions affect each other.

In our case, when forest owner or urbanisation owner resides habitually in the area under risk (this is, “overlapping between exposed-to-bad group residential location and public bad location”) would be more probable aware of the danger and the potential losses, and hence with a higher demand for fire protection. Given the nature of the problem, the preventive resource (herbs and shrubs) spatially coincides with the area under public bad risk.

“Level of public bad prevention demand” is for the plain citizen low and only in summer with catastrophic events a higher awareness arises. There is no a gradual change in demand, but instead a seasonal quick change followed by a rapid falling into oblivion. In general, society is still unaware about these initiatives, what indicates the need of dissemination for a better understanding of herder’s role and the possibilities of collective actions towards these programs and agreements. Only in Andalucía there have been specific campaigns disseminating this task. In

Catalonia, donors have issued the respective press release when contributing to a specific project, and municipalities do also often publicize the agreements to the local or county media.

“High levels of dependence by exposed-to-bad group members on the goods under risk” is far to apply in the studied cases. Forest owners are generally not only dependent on the silvicultural business but they generally combine with other activities; majority of urban citizens can visit alternative forests if one happens to be burnt. In addition, WUI building are often second houses for weekend and/or vocational periods; these not-continuous benefits reduces owner’s interest in fire prevention investments. Neither is high the “dependence of preventive agents on the preventive resource” because herders can get alternative grazing areas and ultimately alternative jobs. Except for the CAT1 and CAT2 cases, where herders derive a substantial part of their income from the fire preventive programs, “*what they get with these payments is a complement; they should search for complementary pastures*” (A3) hence not being fully dependent on the pasture resource in fuelbreaks.

“Fairness in allocation of benefits” relates to the Ostrom (1990) principle of “proportional equivalence between benefits and costs”. Questionnaires show that payments are seen as a deserved reward for the effort incurred by shepherds due to grazing in less attractive areas for their business: “*The RAPCA is thought to be a service*” (A7)”. In fact, 86% of respondents disagree with the idea that “*Participating herders would execute the same work without the program*”, explained through the current opportunity costs: “*Due to the decrease in pastoral activity [in the last decades] it increases the availability of alternative lands*” (A1), and hence herders would not be eager to move: “*Given that currently they [herders] have more than enough food near corrals, for sure they would not move further, where generally forest areas to be protected are located*” (C3). In terms of additionality, these extra efforts would justify the payment. However, it must be kept in mind that still “*In some cases this already happens: herders pasture fuelbreaks which are in the area where their flock usually move and are not rewarded*” (C1), and “*Only in very concrete areas this [not having alternative lands] would occur*” (V1). Once these herders get aware about the existence of payment programs, they may change their behaviour in order to see their monetary rewards increased. This side effect has been highlighted in the literature as possible “*result from mainstreaming of utilitarian market-based rationales for conservation, in terms of both possible changes in the motivational aspects for conservation, as well as in terms of exportation of particular worldviews in the understanding of the human–nature relation*” (Gómez-Baggethun et al, 2010).

There is no consensus on the adequacy of the amount paid: near half of respondents do agree with “*herders think the amount they receive does not correspond to losses and nuisances they incur*”, and the other half disagrees with the statement. Some acknowledge that “*Actually, the payment is symbolic*” (A5) or “*In general the perception of the shepherd is that it is not much, but less is nothing*” (A1). On the other side, others state “*In general they [shepherds] are happy with the payment. Otherwise they wouldn’t do that*” (A3) and “*This is usual in any regime of [compensatory] primes*” (V1). Martínez Tuna and Kosoy (2007) found that for a watershed PES in Honduras, the payment to upstream farmers did not cover their opportunity costs in terms of loss of crops, at maximum in 3%. This finding contrasts with market logic, by which farmers should not accept such agreements. Authors, then, attribute their willingness to enter into contracts to a social feeling of group membership and a collective awareness (it could be interpreted as solidarity to group consuming water downstream). In our case, it would mean that herders are willing to participate due to a solidarity sentiment towards those potentially suffering from fire. However, when asked about the possibility that “*herders participating have a sense of duty in the security of forests in their area*” there is no clear convergent reply among respondents. “*Rather than a sense of duty, their co-responsibility stems from the self-esteem aspects and the professional acknowledgment (economically reinforced) that generates the RAPCA [network] and the proximity of technicians that follow up their field work*” (A7). The local degree of herders engagement should be taken into account when designing the program and deciding whether monetary or in-kind rewards, as experimental evidence indicates that monetary incentives can crowd out social approval incentives and thereby result in a decrease in contributions (see survey by Fehr and Falk, 2001).

Regarding WUI urbanizations, it would not be considered as fair if the maintenance of their perimeters is covered by the general municipal budget, given that the effect is improving private houses conditions. Compensated effects would take place if municipality devotes an equivalent budget for other municipal services for inhabitants outside the WUI areas.

Respondents fully converge in disagreeing from *“considering the payment as an indirect transfer to herders, as a group with low resources, hence being a measure of reduction or rural inequalities”* justifying that *“It is not a subsidy, but a professional contract for professionals, whose labour is evaluated before paying”* (A7).

4. Institutional arrangements

Devising rules on the common problem influences in perception of legitimacy and enforcement. Collective-choice rules affect who is involved in deciding about future rules and how preferences will be aggregated (Ostrom et al, 2009).

All the questionnaires received disagreed with the statement that *“shepherds count with a self-control system”*, revealing that the effective control is exerted by Government. Most respondents also disagreed with *“pastures in forests are considered as a collective good by the local community”*, pointing out that this absolutely does not occur in private forests; this shows that even without physical barriers, private forests are respected. A few have reported that collective pastures could be potentially perceived so only in some municipal forests. There are varied opinions on *“there are conflicts among shepherds using the pastures”*, specifying in most cases that they are punctual and concern pasture zones' assignment or accidents (animals escaping and causing some damages). The partial privatisation of harvesting rights in public forests through concession contracts may facilitate individualistic behaviours. In fact respondents have reported sentences in this line: *“each shepherd is a world; it is a sector where one exploitation is very different from others, where each individual organises by his own”* (C2); *“the rest of shepherds go by their own”* (A3). This overall framework may preclude the emergence of locally devised norms. Though individualism, associations provide a platform of discussion and coordinated action.

Even the individualism and distance, there is some sort of confidence among them. It is surprising that some respondent report that participant herders *“have trust in each other in order not to leave others in a bad position”* (C3); *“because we are interested in maintaining the job, and secondly because it can be extended to the entire territory and others can benefit”* (C4). This would support the “genuine altruists” classification of Ostrom et al (1999). However, also *“Unfortunately this is not exactly like this, and there are people only thinking in getting money...”* (C4).

Regarding “graduated sanctioning”, all respondents report a low degree of flexibility in punishing lack of compliance. Sanctions may go from the reduction in the monetary amount, extinction of payment right, to no renovation of agreement in the coming season, lack of eligibility for next call or loss of grazing rights in a specific forest.

“Accountability” is demonstrated by means of the follow-up of the programs, either by scientists or forest guards. Urbanisations may not count with such control; however municipal staff or buildings' owner may directly control the impacts achieved and complain if they do not follow the agreed terms.

An instrument potentially influencing preventive measures is the fire insurance. In the US, housing insurance premium does depend on the degree of vulnerability to fire, decreasing the price with lower risk (Brueckner, 1981). If that premium reduction would constitute a significant percentage, it could stimulate WUI urbanisations' owners reacting toward reducing fire risk. Nevertheless it should be taken into account that contracting insurance entails intrinsic problems of moral hazard and adverse selection¹⁸. Therefore, facilitating housing insurance or establishing

¹⁸ “Moral hazard refers to the fact that the insured person's optimal decision may change as a result of taking out insurance. Because the insurance contract reduces the loss associated with the insured event, such changes in behaviour will normally increase the probability of the insured event occurring. Adverse selection refers to the fact that people who are more likely to

its obligatory contract is not necessarily conducive to increased preventive measures. A parallel reasoning may take place with forest insurance for private forest owners: those owners with insurance would not have incentives to better protect their forests if the payment to be received equals or exceeds the expected lost value. Picos and Valero (2005) identify for Spain the operational difficulties for insurance companies to engage in covering the full patrimonial value (or commercial value of timber). They analyse other insurance forms, as follows: (i) investment recovery, (ii) payment of reforestation and infrastructure expenses and (iii) agreed value. Investment recovery calculation depends on insurer's criteria on eligible incurred expenses. Reposition costs do not cover losses from marketable burnt material nor the executed investments. An agreed amount counts with asymmetrical information from both parts. These authors foresee that preventive silvicultural practices may influence in the insurance cost, and suggest a bonus for those locations with less risk and adequate practices. Picos and Valero (2005) recommend for small forest owners the reposition cost method. These authors advise to restrict the consideration of fire insurance only for productive forests, being in goods or services for his owner or to society, but in this last case only when the owner is somehow compensated, which is not the often situation. Consequently, insurances would not contemplate the loss of intangible, non-commercial values that landowner holds. Given that recovering the forest conditions is a long lasting process, owners may have other incentives to avoid such time gap by investing in fire preventive measures that improve forest resilience and hence a more rapid recovery of forest in the event of fire; this is especially true if those measures have side-benefits that increase tree growth and overall forest productivity. Obliging forest owners to contract an insurance is neither necessary nor sufficient to induce the execution of preventive measures.

On the other side, obliging forest owners to full cover fire preventive measures may collude with the financial situation of each individual, while simultaneously not recognising the public benefits their forest provide. As mentioned above, a crucial factor that give incentives for the actual execution of fire preventive measures in forest owner self interest is whether s/he perceives them as synergic with the forest plan: e.g. those owners not investing in forest improvement will likely not recognise such synergy, but instead an additional, not contemplated cost; those with the "untouching forests" paradigm may collude with the fire preventive interventions; and those who regularly conduct improvement treatments forests may find these measures as compatible or even facilitating other silvicultural activities.

Berry (2007) suggests policies that emphasizing fuels reduction and homeowner responsibility in the wildland-urban interface would help in achieving a more efficient use of public budget. In the case studies, achieving more WUI perimeter protected is expected to derive from a mandatory approach. Ill-definition of final responsible or insufficient control of its implementation may not lead to the desired outcomes. On the contrary, in cases where effective normative measures that oblige the direct beneficiaries to take care of their own fire prevention may also induce to programmes alike.

5. External environment

"Technology" seems not to constitute a constraint: the diverse methods for fire prevention are available; however, pasturing appears to be more feasible as in some location they already count with a herder and not with the required machinery. In addition, the technological process of cattle breeding is well-known by their implementers, and only some changes in their "working manner" should be applied for fire prevention grazing. Those changes are generally well-accepted if the required infrastructures are facilitated: *"if they are offered a minimum of basic conditions (water, hut for overnight, complementary food if need...) herders will go"* (C2). "Time adaptation" is recognised as relevant, as shown by the pilot period in most cases, in view of learning from the most adequate animal type, requirements, etc. More difficult is the "technology for exclusion" of the benefits of fire prevention, given their accessible nature.

suffer the insured event will be more willing to insure at a given rate. If the insurance company cannot detect such people, then losses will occur" (Quiggin et al, 1994).

A very relevant point represents “external markets”. There is a large expectation in a system that combines mechanical treatments with pastoral maintenance, seen as potentially more economically sustainable than only traditional mechanical interventions. Reasons are the reduced costs for the public administration (Dopazo et al, 2012; Varela et al, 2008) while it also provides a marketable product (income possibilities) for the herder. Ideally the system would be self-sustaining, with herders getting interesting revenues so that they don’t need a government payment; this is, the traditional market activity would finance the fire prevention programme: *“I defend that if we live from what we produce (meat, milk, cheese...) grazing in firebreak areas may not imply pay some money to the herder”* (C4). Nevertheless it is likely that better market prices would discourage herders to incur in difficult activities as the required for fire prevention. *“The lower profitability of traditional exploitation, the larger the need to go to other financing sources”* (A3); *“If with cattle product sale they could live, surely they would not move away from their corrals habitually in the town surroundings, and as a consequence they would not enter into programs like these”* (C3). Market prices does not internalise the external effects; hence, a system though to finance herder’s effort through market would be sensible to price volatility. Questionnaires have mentioned the multiple benefits of the program for society in general, what justifies using tax-payers money for at least partly finance the system: *“Benefits obtained are impossible to quantify in economic terms”* (A6); *“There are many other indirect benefits a part of fuel control”* (V1).

The lower dependence of participating herders in market products potentially could entail a reduction of market prices paid to herders. Questionnaires do not show influence of these programs in market prices: *“there is no relationship with price decrease, in fact program participation is punctual of very few herders”* (C1), *“Prices depend on other factors”* (A2); *“Meat price variations are very difficult to understand and related basically with the balance imports/exports of meat, and with consumers’ patterns”* (C1)

Near 80% of respondents perceive that transactions costs are low when compared to the value of benefits produced: *“No [bureaucracy costs are higher than benefits], if we talk in terms of conventional economy and very far from it if we talk about externalities”* (A7); *“No, because mechanical maintenance is more expensive of what a herder may draw”* (C1); *“No. How much does it cost the extinction of one forest fire? Much more”* (V3).

The problem of public funding uncertainty arises in critical budgetary periods as we are currently facing, when these agreements may fall in secondary priorities or even not count with a continuation (e.g. Valencia since 2009): *“Even with consolidated experience, [fire preventive grazing programs] are not endowed with budget in the same predisposition that those devoted to “untouchable” items”* (C4). This result supports the public good characteristic of “allocation decisions primarily made by political process” (Ostrom and Ostrom, 1977). The overall perception is that diminishing funding for these schemes would be an error, as being a medium-term policy proved to be more efficient than other measures.

Some programmes have been punctually sponsored. Such donors become key for the start-up of the initiatives, especially in those involving private-private agreements. Given the lack of medium or long term commitment capacity of such entities, it would be interesting that such funds are devoted to the costly, long-term investments that would be more difficult to face by participating agents in later periods (as being done in CAT3). Donors that are not directly beneficiaries could act as complementary sources for extraordinary expenses, given that financial risk arises when program’s design heavily relies on them for its normal functioning. Flexibility for complementing service contract with grants from other sources potentially increases herders’ interest in participating; e.g. combining forest owners-herders agreements with agro-environmental grants is possible; however it must be take into account that if a reward is considered as “fair” by itself, this overlapping may cause double payment for the same item.

All questionnaires responded that nowadays other beneficiaries (e.g. rural tourism businesses) do not contribute in financing fire prevention programs. Imitating a “tourist tax” in business in coastal areas earmarked to maintain beaches, also in rural areas business benefiting from green scenery (e.g. adventure sports, campings, rural hotels,

rustic restaurants) could charge their clients for that maintenance. However, there is no debate on this point, most likely justified by the already existing intrinsic difficulties of the rural tourism sector.

From the demographic point of view, facilitating revenues for shepherds do help in fixing population in rural areas. One of the regular identified problems in the literature is the unclear the new generational continuation in cattle breeding exploitations (Baiges et al, 2007; Besalú et al, 2011). While some respondents have subscribed that idea, there are some positive comments in the sense of a new era in pastoralism, mentioning the herders' schools as well-functioning and very promising initiatives (A1, C2, C3). *"For the future of the program, herders should be further incentivised in order to make [their job] more attractive"* (A6), *"Now we have a group of young herders with large motivation and future"* (C6), but *"It is important to give the program certain stability"* (C2).

"Supporting external governance" and nested level of administrations influence largely bottom-up processes, given that the concerned group does not act in isolation. Naghendra and Ostrom (2012) observe that national, political, and fiscal guidelines often play a prominent role in shaping the level of participation by local politicians, who play an increasingly important role in new and emerging formulations of collaborative and/or decentralized governance. Alongside, alliances and networks at the local level also impact trajectories of decision-making and change. But also horizontal coordination among technicians of different departments do influence. These pose a great challenge due to the traditional low degree of interaction between departments with competences in agriculture, forests and fire extinction. This usually contrasts with farmers' view, which integrates all land uses in a holistic territorial concept. The lack of interaction may be caused either by the lack of spaces for common work or by the divergence in values and paradigms. First may be explained by physical constraints or inexistence of common platforms; both are relatively easy to overcome. However, a more challenging scenario appears when agents do not share common values. These programs follow the current trend of multidisciplinary teams working towards a better coordination between agencies for rural land management. Such approach is likely to create a social capital and settle the ground for future policies with shared values and paradigms. Still, respondents mostly disagree with *"the program has attained a coordination between agencies"*; however, there are a few encouraging comments *"there is a jointly working group"* (A3) and *"let's hope so with the new reorganisation"* (A1).

6. Facilitating features

Even if Agrawal (2003) did not mentioned them, scholar literature and questionnaires have revealed side benefits that create synergies with other policies of rural development and farm biodiversity conservation. This result would be consistent with the possible scope economies in public good provision (Duncombe and Yinger, 1993), because they share inputs (e.g. herder's job) and by-products (e.g. change into native species).

Grazing programs for fire prevention entail the public recognition of shepherd's activities, increasing their visibility and dignifying this profession. Only one respondent didn't agree with the statement *"local community (formal or informally) is aware of and respects shepherd's prevention role. It supposes a kind of social acknowledgment/pride that shepherds receive"*. The dignification of shepherds' job was in fact one of the needs identified in the "Guardabosc" meeting (FMR and CaixaCatalunya, 2010). Respondants indicate the relevance of *"Anyone would like to be recognise, even more if they come from a traditionally negatively seen sector"*(A6), *"[Local community] acknowledges the great task (...) This is very important for them, their self-confidence and pride of being a herder"* (C3).

During the "green revolution" very productive races were introduced in the country, and nowadays there is a movement towards recovering indigenous cattle races. Autochthonous races show more adaptation to physical and biological environmental factors (FMR and CaixaCatalunya, 2010) and hence more appropriate for current and foreseen vegetation conditions. These programs bolstering stress situations to the flock would then incentive herders to use more rustic animals and hence maintaining native races (Baiges et al, 2007; Besalú et al, 2011). Some

regions do also monetarily support through the agro-environmental CAP grants, by establishing specific lines; they are generally not compatible with other measures such as the grazing in PPP (DOGC, 2011).

7. Other initiatives

Finally, it is worth noting that there are other initiatives of payments to shepherds. First, the inspiring initiative is the one implemented in Southern France and Corsica since 1990 as pilot and since 1993 with the agro-environmental measures. They established the Network of Fuel Breaks, which was composed not only by traditional firebreaks, but also by the Pastoral Reinforcement Zones. In 2000, 700 cattle exploitations participated covering over 32.000ha (Thavaud, 2006). The program in Andalusia adapts most of its philosophy.

In the region of Aragón, the Environmental Plan of Extensive Stockbreeding started in 2005 as a pilot and was launched with more ambitious objectives in 2008. The programme is similar to the Andalusian one, with the peculiarity that not only contracts with herders have been implemented, but also in some small case the government has got the direct management of animals. In Aragón herders do not receive a monetary reward, but instead they become infrastructure (Ruiz-Mirazo, 2011), what reduces their productive costs.

The “Plan 42” in Castilla-León responds to other problem: fires provoked by herders in order to improve pasture quality. Framed in the CAP agro-environmental measures, herders can apply for a grant for improving pastures by diverse means. For being eligible, herders must subscribe a Territorial Exploitation Contract with the public administration that lasts for 5 years. Such contract involves the elaboration of a silvopastoral plan, which organises pasture improvements actions according to herders’ will but overviewed by a technician. The main measure proposed has been brushcutting and their maintenance, which in some cases has been financed by public funds. It is reported that since the implementation of the measure, there has been a substantial (up to 80%) reduction of fires with this cause in the main problematic zones (Ruiz-Mirazo, 2011). It has been reported that the facts of writing a medium/long-term planning jointly with longer grazing rights allows for a larger attachment of the herder with the areas, *“enforcing individual use of public pastures in contrast with collective use. In this way herder becomes responsible of maintenance and improvement of the lands, overcoming traditional abandonment of communal lands”* (Picardo, unpublished). This rationale follows the “commons’ tragedy”, which in this case does not end in a damage for the group of user of the resource, but instead in the society in general as they cause forest fires. Also in Castilla-León, but in line with the private-private agreements are being tested in Valladolid by a private forest owners association, financially supported by an environmental foundation¹⁹. This last case would be in line with the cooperative, voluntary agreements in Catalonia.

Conclusions

While Southern and Eastern Mediterranean countries suffer forest-related problems originated in an overuse of the resource, Northern countries are facing increasing challenges due to forest abandonment. Property rights and institutions may help to explain the overuse situation, and largely determine duties and benefits of agents affected by a public bad such as fire risk.

Fire prevention constitutes a public service provided by government in order to ensure an acceptable level of risk to citizenship. Public bad do affect negatively collectives; hence, in principle exposed-to-risk agents face incentives to proceed towards fire reduction in a decentralized manner, either individually or associated in a sort of collective-action spontaneous initiatives. Preventive measures can be conducted either by the same agents under risk (becoming co-producers of the public good) or entrusted to a third agent. If appropriately informed and accomplishing features that facilitate interaction among agents under risk and preventive agents, theoretically it

¹⁹ “Prevención de incendios forestales con ganado caprino en superficie forestal privada en Valladolid”. Web: <http://www.pfcyl.es/lineadeactuacion/prevenci-n-de-incendios-forestales-con-ganado-caprino-en-superficie-forestal-privad> [consulted: 29/08/2012]

could be possible a coordinated reaction to prevent such public bad. It does not mean that the Government should not play any role or be restricted to activities such as technical support, oversight and monitoring. Instead, collective action may complement public service provision help in reducing the overall risk. The studied cases present different examples of economic incentives to herders for grazing in fire-strategic areas in view of reducing fire risk, that involve public-private and private-private agreements. The framework of institutional factors that facilitate a durable governance of a collective consumption resource has been applied for cross-comparison of the emergence and management of these socio-ecological systems.

The results of this study bring to light that in most of the cases collective action from beneficiaries is missing or reduced, being the government role crucial to the prevention of the public bad. Government involvement is present in all cases in different degrees and is justified by the conservation of forest externalities to society at large. This is especially true in public-owned forests (CAT1, AND), devoted to provision of social amenities, biodiversity conservation or erosion prevention prior to timber exploitation. Where private benefits accrue, results show that external (usually public) support is required for catalyzing agreements and covering start-up expenses.

The compiled information allows for affirming that the problem of bush accumulation is relatively recent, whereas successful collective actions are commonly linked to long-lasting processes. In general, society is still unaware about the possibilities of bad prevention and of these initiatives. Government is attributed the duty for risk reduction, not only in fire extinction but also as expert to demark fire-strategic areas. This strong role, jointly with the lack of experience in collective problems may preclude for successful, spontaneous self-management solutions. However, there is a large expectation in this system, seen as potentially more sustainable than the traditional mechanical interventions, given the intrinsic interest of agents not to get burnt, the reduced costs in comparison to other preventive alternatives while it also provides a marketable product. Secondary benefits accrue: an innovation in the social role of herders, incentives for indigenous cattle races maintenance and better coordination between government departments for rural land management. Compensation payments are seen as a deserved reward for the effort incurred by herders due to grazing in less attractive areas for their business. Private owners agreements with herders are more likely to take place in areas with a very dynamic forest sector, high risk perception and with a potential grant for herders. Normative measures that oblige the largest beneficiaries to take care of their own fire prevention may also induce to similar programmes.

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ANNEX 1: Questionnaire responses

	Completely agree	Agree	Disagree	Completely disagree	Don't know
1. There is a local herder “leader”. His/her opinion about the program becomes key for the rest of herders to engage or not in the program and accomplish the acquired commitments	7%	43%	36%	7%	7%
2. Program implementation largely depends on a key person. There is a risk that when this person dissociates from the program it does not continue any longer, given that there is no interest from others.	14%	36%	36%	7%	7%
3. It becomes difficult that herders adapt their pasturing manner because they are old and are not accustomed to changing environments	0	29%	43%	21%	7%
4. Similar past experiences (e.g. FDG) have helped in program implementation	21%	14%	29%	7%	29%
5. At the beginning there were negative reactions from herders' side, because they interpreted that the program constituted an external imposition to their traditional way of managing pasture zones	0%	14%	50%	21%	14%
6. It is difficult that a program like this emerges privately because it is very expensive. In addition, the effect of grazing lasts very short time and exists a large uncertainty about its usefulness	7%	29%	43%	14%	7%
7. One should take advantage of the “momentum”: society in general is only aware about wildfires when forest is burn, and then it is easier to accept paying for preventions.	29%	36%	21%	0%	14%
8. Herders have participated in firebreaks demarcation. They identify and understand selection criteria. There has never been discussions with technicians for this reason.	7%	36%	36%	7%	14%
9. Participating herders have a “sense of duty” of their contribution to security of forests in their area	14%	43%	21%	7%	14%
10. The expenses related to bureaucracy, initial planning, herders' selection, surveillance, payment procedures, etc exceeds benefits provided by the program.	7%	0%	36%	43%	14%
11. In general, herders assume that their descendants will not continue with pasturing. In addition, extensive livestock breeding is becoming less profitable. Hence, this program has no future in the long term.	7%	29%	29%	21%	14%
12. Herders think that the amount they receive does not correspond to losses/annoyances they incur. Technicians do not perceive the same.	0%	43%	50%	0%	7%
13. Participating herders would do the same work also without the program, given that they do not have further alternatives of pasture zones.	0%	14%	50%	36%	0%

14. There are local business that benefit from a lower fire risk but do not contribute to its financing (i.e. rural tourism businesses)	29%	50%	0%	0%	21%
15. It is difficult for herders to <i>in situ</i> identify where do they have to work with animals (e.g. it is not well demarked).	0%	14%	43%	43%	0%
16. The role of other local agents is crucial for the well-functioning of the program (e.g. teacher, mayor, police, priest...)	21%	36%	14%	21%	7%
17. Participating herders do not generally receive sanctions if they do not accomplish, even if they exist. There is flexibility from guards or other controls.	7%	7%	43%	29%	14%
18. It is a direct transfer to herders, who are the agents with lowest resources in rural areas. It is, hence, more a program of inequality reduction rather than efficiency in risk reduction.	0%	0%	29%	64%	7%
19. There are evidences of conflicts among herders using pasture zones	0%	36%	14%	29%	21%
20. Local community (formal or informally) knows and respects the role of herder in prevention. It supposes a sort of acknowledgement/pride that herders receive.	43%	36%	7%	0%	14%
21. Each herder knows what himself and others are allowed to pasture. There is communication among herders.	21%	50%	14%	0%	14%
22. Participating herders control each other whether everyone accomplishes his commitments so that the program is successful. They have their own control and sanctioning system.	0%	14%	29%	29%	29%
23. Herders shouldn't be paid for a task that they did before for free	0%	7%	14%	71%	0%
24. It is difficult that herders participate in this program because supposes a very big effort for them (walking long distance, lower pasture quality, more time devoted for overseeing cattle...).	0%	29%	64%	7%	0%
25. Market price variations have notably influenced participation and accomplishment levels	14%	21%	14%	14%	29%
26. Pasture zones in forests are considered as a collective good that belongs to local community.	0%	36%	36%	14%	14%
27. Herders' associations do not support this program because it has lowered meat prices	0%	0%	43%	36%	21%
28. The urbanizations in forest-urban interface zones contribute to the payment of perimeters' cleaning	0%	71%	0%	14%	14%
29. The program has improved the coordination between the agency responsible for stockbreeding issues with the forest fire agency	0%	13%	50%	38%	0
30. With current crisis it is likely that government decides devoting these funds to other priorities.	22%	56%	0%	0%	22%

Annex 2. Model of controlled grazing for fire prevention

Agent 1: Government

We will consider here Government as the agency or department with competences in fire prevention and extinction, and in livestock. In the real world they are three different agencies with differentiated budgets and competences.

Objective function: $Max W = \alpha_{R_W} \cdot R_W + \beta \cdot X$

W: Welfare of overall population

R_W : Existing wildfire risk. $\alpha_{R_W} < 0$

X: Other goods and services for citizens; $\beta > 0$

Assumptions: Regional level or with competences in fire prevention and extinction, tax establishment and collection power. We compute all for a year, this is, annual budget assignment. There are different levels of accepted fire risk for each social agent i (γ_i); government's first objective should be ensuring an overall accepted risk (γ_T) and later helping other agents to reach their own levels. We assume each citizen pays a tax t . We assume there is one single shepherd for the entire region, or equivalently, there is a single shepherds association that channels all shepherds work (pays their grazing fees for the entire area, and negotiates with government and private landowners). We also assume that all the public forests for grazing are strategic areas for wildfire prevention; hence, all S= PPP. In public forests, infrastructure for grazing is under the responsibility of the government. Finally, we assume that government does not extract revenues from timber.

Budget restriction: $M = t \cdot n + G_{fee} \cdot S = C_{br} \cdot br + C_{ext} \cdot ext + C_{infr} \cdot infr + C_X \cdot X$

M: Total public budget

t: citizens' tax

n: citizen n , $T = \sum_1^T n$

C_i : Cost of i ; $i = \{br, ext, infr, X\}$ where br: annual biomass reduction; ext: annual fire extinction; infr: infrastructures for grazing

G_{fee} : grazing fee (€/ha); S: area of public forests devoted for grazing (ha)

X: Other goods and services for citizens; $\beta > 0$

Technological restrictions:

Assumptions: Biomass reduction is the only factor affecting risk of wildfire. We also assume that fire prevention activities take place in the same year, we will approximate by assigning their corresponding annual expenses: e.g. if grazing is annual but mechanical interventions take place each 3 years, we will compute here the 100% cost/ha of grazing and 1/3 of the mechanical cost/ha. Cost of mechanical intervention is higher than grazing costs, which are the monetary rewards to shepherds. Infrastructure needed for shepherds involves water points, fencing, refugees building or improving grass quality to complement the existing ones (naturally provided springs w or grazing plants).

Risk reduction process: $R_W = f(\alpha_B \cdot B_t)$; $\alpha_B < 0$; $R_W \leq \gamma_T$

B_t : understorey/shrubs biomass at time t : $B_t = B_{t-1} + \Delta b$; $\Delta b = b_{growth} - br$

Δb : annual variation of biomass

b_{growth} : natural growth of understorey biomass

Biomass reduction process: $br = S_{grazed} + \delta \cdot S_{mech}$

S_{grazed} : forest area under controlled grazing; if no program: $S_{grazed}=0$

S_{mech} : forest area under mechanical shrubcutting and fuelbreak maintenance

$\delta \in [0,1]$: reduction in mechanical interventions due to grazing; if no program: $\delta = 1$

Hence, cost of biomass reduction: $C_{br} \cdot br = C_{grazing} \cdot S_{grazed} + C_{mech} \cdot \delta \cdot S_{mech}$

Hypothesis: If $\uparrow \delta \rightarrow$ more incentives for using grazing as preventive tool

Fire extinction process: $ext = f(\alpha_{ext} \cdot B_t)$; $\alpha_{ext} > 0$

Hypothesis: If $\nabla(C_{ext} \cdot ext) \cdot p_{fire} \geq \Delta(C_{br} \cdot br) \rightarrow br = max; ext = 0$; p_{fire} : probability of fire. This is, if the expected reduction in extinction costs would be higher or equivalent to the cost in biomass reduction, there would be incentives for Government to devote those resource to the preventive activities. In the real world this is not always feasible, because there should be a minimum budget for contingency, this is: $C_{ext} \cdot ext > 0$, and there is a large uncertainty on fire probability.

Infrastructures provision process: $C_{infr} \cdot infr = FC_i \cdot infr + MC_{infr-i} \cdot (infr - i)$

Infr=f(w', ref, fences, g'): complement of water or pastures, building refugees or fences

FC_i: fixed cost of building new infrastructure i

MC_{infr-i}: annual maintenance costs of the other infrastructures; generally MC_{infr-i} << FC_i

Program intervention: control variables by government

1. In S_{grazed} : **contracting shepherds for reduced biomass maintenance**
2. In FC_i: subsidising fixed cost of building **infrastructures** or the maintenance cost (MC_{infr-i}).
3. In G_{fee}: **eliminating grazing fees** or securing **longer concessions**

Agent 2: Shepherd

Objective function: $Max W_S = (X, L, R)$

X: Goods and services acquired through income

L: Leisure time

R: Social recognition, community acceptance, job satisfaction/proudness

Assumptions: S/he is owner of the animals and has them from previous animals (no purchase). Vaccination and other animals treatments are for free. Forest has two types of pasture areas: one with high quality, palatable pastures, and other with low quality. Fire strategic areas have the low quality. Transaction costs account for the disutility generated through bureaucracy (grant application, payments delay, renovation of pastures' permission). Leisure time depend on the required efforts to control the animals and to move the flock from the refuge to the pastures.

Budget restriction: $I = q \cdot p + CAP \cdot n_{animals} = C_{food} \cdot food + G_{fee} \cdot S + C_X \cdot X + TC$

q: quantity of market product produced (milk, meat, wool)

p: market price of the product

CAP: subsidy from the Common Agrarian Policy

n_{animals}: number of animals

C_f: cost of extra/complementary food

food: extra/complementary food for breeding animals

TC: Transaction costs

Hypothesis: if food price increases sufficiently, it is possible that they attempt to use only pastures, and hence more biomass reduction.

Technological restriction: $S_{grazed} \leq 400ha$; $n_{animals} \leq 1.000 heads$

$$q = q_{type}(food_{type} + g_{type} + w_{type} - \alpha_d \cdot d) \cdot n_{animals}$$

$type = \{bo, eq, ca, ov\}$: type of animal

q_{type} : normal unit production of certain type of animals

g_{type} : pasture food; $g_{type} = g_{high} + g_{low}$; goats can eat g_{low} , sheep and cows prefer g_{high} .

Pastures naturally available jointly with artificially supplied in pastures and in extra food should cover the animals need: $g + g' + food \geq (food_{type} + g_{type}) \cdot n_{animals}$

w_{type} : water consumption needed for certain type of animal; $w_{bo} > w_{ca}, w_{ov}$. Water naturally available jointly with artificially supplied should cover the animals need: $w + w' \geq w_{type} \cdot n_{animals}$

d = distance from refugee to pasture areas. α_d : annual calories consumed per distance walked, what decreases production. If $\uparrow d \rightarrow \downarrow q$ In addition, $d = \frac{1}{L}$

Program intervention:

1. Increasing income through **contract for maintenance of a reduced biomass**, but also reduction of product and increases TC. This is, a direct reward for the service provided.

$$q \cdot p + CAP \cdot n_{animals} + C_{grazing} \cdot S_{grazed} = C_{food} \cdot food + p \cdot \nabla q + G_{fee} \cdot S_{grazed} + C_X \cdot X + TC$$

Assumptions: Effort in bringing animals to difficult areas is inversely proportional to leisure time of shepherd. Effort directly depends on the availability of alternative pasture zones and the control exerted (including sanctions if accomplishing).

$$br = e \cdot n_{animals} \cdot S_{grazed}$$

e : effort of shepherd; $e = f(c, S')$; $e = \frac{1}{L}$

S' : available alternative pastures (with better pasture quality, or nearer)

c : control by payer (government or landowner)

Hence, ideally: $C_{grazing} \cdot S_{grazed} = p \cdot \nabla q(g_{low}) + \Delta TC + \varepsilon$, being ε a bonus that compensates effort (loss of leisure value, jointly with other disutilities such as change in pasture habits, nuisances due to controls/auditories, etc)

2. Agreement for reduced biomass maintenance, by incentivising through **infrastructure** facilitation (building water points, refugees, or seeding). This is an in-kind reward that improves productivity: $\uparrow w, \downarrow d, \uparrow g \rightarrow \uparrow q$ and/or reduces the expenses in complementary food.

$$\text{Hence, ideally: } p \cdot \Delta q(infr) = \nabla C_{food} \cdot food + \Delta TC + \varepsilon.$$

3. Agreement for reduced biomass maintenance, by incentivising through **eliminating G_{fee}** . This is an in-kind reward that diminishes production expenses.

$$q \cdot p + CAP \cdot n_{animals} = C_{food} \cdot food + C_X \cdot X + TC$$

$$\text{Hence, ideally: } G_{fee} \cdot S_{grazed} = p \cdot \nabla q(g_{low}) + \Delta TC + \varepsilon.$$

4. Incentive by **securing longer concessions**, what reduces TC
5. Incentive by increasing the **social recognition**

Agent 3: Forest landowner

Objective function: $Max W_{fo} = f(X_{fo}, (R_W - \gamma_{fo}), U_{amen})$

W_{fo} : Welfare of the forest owner

$R_{W\sim\gamma_{fo}}$: disutility created for the excess of wildfire risk perceived by the forest owner

U_{amen} : Utility provided by other amenities perceived by the forest owner

X_{fo} : Other goods and services expected to be covered with forest revenues

Assumptions: Forest landowner can show some (or all) of the following motivating factors (based on Domínguez and Shannon, 2011): (i) the economic expectations from forests, this is, from seeing forests as a source of revenues ($EI > 0$), or assume that it is not profitable and will incur in any case in some maintenance expenses ($EI < 0$); (ii) the perception of risk of losing the asset, as a differential between own accepted level of fire and actual one, so that those not concerned by fire will have $R_{W\sim\gamma_{fo}}$ what does not induce to reduce risk; (iii) the utility originated in intangible processes, such the moral duty of the owner to maintain a family inheritance, environmental awareness to conserve biodiversity, or use for own recreation. We assume that amenities do not have a cost. Forest products here are simplified as only two: timber and pastures (S).

Budget restriction:

$$EI = p_{timber} \cdot q_{timber} + G_{fee} \cdot S = C_{silv} \cdot silv + C_{br} \cdot br + C_{infr} \cdot infr + C_X \cdot X + c$$

El: Expected revenues from forests owner

silv: silvicultural treatments to forests

c: disutility generated by controlling shepherd's work

Technological restrictions: same biomass reduction process than in government / agent 1 applies

$$q_{timber} = f(silv, br)$$

$$G_{fee} \cdot S = f(infr, g, w)$$

Assumptions: We simplify that timber production depends only on silvicultural treatments to trees and on the reduction of understorey biomass (as reduction of competence to trees). We assume no costs in infrastructure for timber harvesting. The only infrastructure would be for shepherds. Landowner can negotiate higher grazing revenues if the area offered is higher, but also if there are better assets for the shepherd, these are, natural availability of grazing quality and water, but also the artificial infrastructures for those purpose or for fencing.

Hypothesis: if expected timber reduction due to wildfires is higher than the cost of preventive measures, it is likely that the owner will implement them by self motivation:

$$p_{fire} \cdot p_{timber} \cdot \nabla q_{timber} > C_{br} \cdot br$$

Hypothesis: if cost of infrastructure is lower or equivalent to grazing fees, then there is a net drop in biomass reduction costs. In this case, landowner would be motivated to provide the necessary infrastructure.

$$G_{fee} \cdot S \geq C_{infr} \cdot infr \rightarrow \nabla C_{br} \cdot br$$

Program intervention:

1. **Contract shepherd for reduced biomass maintenance**
2. Agreement of interchange: reduced biomass maintenance for the necessary **infrastructure** to shepherd. This will occur only if cost of infrastructure is lower than the gains in preventive costs. $C_{infr} \cdot infr \leq \nabla C_{br} \cdot br$
3. Agreement of interchange: reduced biomass maintenance for releasing the **grazing fee** to shepherd. This will occur only if losses due to grazing fees are lower than gains in preventive costs $G_{fee} \cdot S \leq \nabla C_{br} \cdot br$

Agent 4: WUI house owner

Objective function: $Max W_{WUI} = f(\varphi \cdot R_{WUI}, X_{WUI})$

W_{WUI} : Welfare of the owners of houses in the Wildland-Urban Interface (WUI).

R_{WUI} : Existing wildfire risk overall in the WUI area, expected losses in case of fire

$\varphi \in [0,1]$: factor of perception of wildfire risk; $\varphi = 0$ when no risk is perceived (no awareness) and $\varphi = 1$ when the actual risk is fully perceived.

X_{WUI} : Other goods and services

Assumptions: a municipality counts with inhabitants in a wildland urban interface urbanization (WUI) and in the center of the town. The wildfire risk in urbanisations is higher than in the center $R_{WUI} > R_{center}$. To decrease such risk, maintenance of the biomass in the perimeter of buildings in the WUI can be done. Residents can contract a house insurance. Such insurance premium (b) takes into account the house location in a WUI zone, increasing the price if no maintenance of perimeters is done regularly. In reality, this detailed differentiation may not be done in Spain. On the other hand, city hall can establish and charge municipal taxes for services offered.

Budget restriction: $M_{WUI} = C_{br} \cdot br + ins + C_X \cdot X$

M_{WUI} : budget of the owner of a building in the WUI, assumed state variable.

$ins = b_0 + \mu \cdot b_{WUI}$: insurance payment; b_0 = basic premium, corresponds to other contingencies than fire; b_{WUI} = extra premium due to location in a risky area; $\mu \in [0,1]$ discount if preventive measures are taken regularly.

$\theta \cdot p_{fire} - ins > \varphi \cdot R_{WUI}$: when perception on losses is lower than the insurance coverage in case of fire (θ) deducted the cost of the insurance, then people will contract an insurance.

Hypothesis: Spontaneous preventive actions may emerge from WUI owners if there is a mandatory house insurance (equivalent to $\varphi = 1$), whose fire risk extra cost is higher than preventive measures. $C_{br} \cdot br < \mu \cdot b_{WUI}$

Technological restriction: same biomass reduction technology than Government/agent 1.

Legal restriction: if law mandates reducing risk, then municipality must incur in biomass reduction action in order to achieve an acceptable level of risk: $R_{WUI} = \gamma_{WUI}$

Program intervention:

5. establishment of a **specific charge** t_{WUI} for owners of buildings in WUI urbanisations without own preventive measures in place by a WUI neighbours association that directly contract the preventive services.

Assumptions: We assume that urbanisation are close to the shepherds corral, with water availability, and hence no extra infrastructure is required; however in reality this may not happen and hence they would incur in $C_{infr} \cdot infr$

WUI budget constraint: $M_{WUI} = t_{WUI} + C_X \cdot X + Coord$

Coord: disutility originated in coordination efforts among WUI neighbours. These may stem from willingness to cooperate from WUI owners, or the level of disagreements in the techniques to be used (e.g. nuisances perceived due to cattle near houses).

Hence, ideally: $t_{WUI} \cdot n_{WUI} = C_{br} \cdot br$.

Neighbours' association will face incentives towards reducing expenses in preventive measures in view of reducing the fee. It would be more likely that they select a combination of grazing and mechanical actions.

6. establishment of a **specific municipal charge** t_{WUI} for owners of buildings in WUI urbanisations without own preventive measures. The municipality contracts the services.

Assumptions: City hall has the competences to establish a specific charge.

$$\text{WUI budget constraint: } M_{WUI} = t_{WUI} + C_X \cdot X$$

$$\text{Municipal budget constraint: } M_{town} = t_{town} \cdot n_{town} + t_{WUI} \cdot n_{WUI} = C_X \cdot X_{mun} + C_{br} \cdot br$$

t_{town} : regular municipal taxes to all citizens

X_{mun} : Other municipal services

Municipality may not face the same incentives for reducing expenses in preventive measures, unless they expect to get some municipal revenues for the intermediary service. Municipality may face other incentives, such as maintaining traditional jobs (*trad*) or to conduct a more close-to-nature intervention (*eco*): e.g. $Max W_{town} = f(R_{town}, X_{town}, trad, eco)$